

**Electronic, didactic and innovative platform for learning
based on multimedia assets**

e-DIPLOMA

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D.4.3 Course Prototypes

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3 Introduction

3.1 Executive Summary

This document is the documentation component of deliverable D4.3 of e-DIPLOMA project, which accompanies the software constituting the essence of this deliverable. The software is a collection of educational content, consisting of *modules*, organized into *prototypes*.

The document summarizes the results of

- T4.4: Development of Prototype 1 and post-evaluation adaptation (Lead: UJI)
- T4.5: Development of Prototype 2 and post-evaluation adaptation (Lead: BME)
- T4.6: Development of Prototype 3 and post-evaluation adaptation (Lead: TUD)

Section 4.2 describes the original concepts of the prototypes as envisioned in the Grant Agreement.

Section 4.3 explains the changes enacted during the co-design phase, and specifies course content covered by this demonstrator.

Section 5 provides the technical background for the development of applications for the e-DIPLOMA Platform in general, in the form of software packages that facilitate the integration of applications, and in particular multiplayer activities.

Section 6 contains the module descriptions for all the three packages. Section titles in this part indicate the number of the prototype and the number of the module they belong to. For all modules

- the activity flow,
- operational mechanisms,
- technical background,
- data capture capabilities,
- and a description of user actions (mostly in the style of a user manual)

is provided. For individual modules, additional content may be provided. In particular, algorithmic aspects of simulation-type activities are described. Most modules are accessed and launched following standard operational procedures of the e-DIPLOMA platform, but for P2M3 “Painters”, a step-by-step guide for operating all elements (Moodle, the e-DIPLOMA Platform, remote desktop, MS Teams, Edison) is provided. As in this module the role of the supervising teacher is important, the document includes instructions not only for the student users, but also separately for the teacher.

Finally, instructions are given on how to access and test the demonstrators (but see Section 3.5 on how security issues regarding these have been addressed).

3.2 Relation to Other Project Documents

This document is most directly related to previous documents

- **D4.2 E-platform software**, as the demonstrated modules are fully or partially integrated with the platform, and can be accessed and launched using procedures described in D4.2,

- **D5.2 Definition of appropriate metrics for the assessment of learning competencies**, as the modules are set up to record data according to the specified metrics,
- **D3.2 Visualization and interaction demonstrators implementing new techniques and traditional ones**, as some software features in both deliverables with a different focus.

Later documents directly based on this deliverable are

- **D3.5 Testing and Piloting Conclusion report**, which contains documentation on testing and piloting, the development process, and the final version of the modules demonstrated as a prototype here,
- **D5.3 System usability and validation report and ergonomics of evaluation measures**, which contains the results of the usability studies, the validation studies, and the ergonomics of the modules demonstrated here,
- **D5.5 Social and educational impact report**, which evaluates the social and educational impact of the modules demonstrated here, and the educational and technological methods featured in them,
- **D2.1 Best practices report**, which documents pilots as good practice case studies.

3.3 Abbreviation List

Among the acronyms used most often in the present document are, in alphabetical order, the following:

AI: Artificial intelligence

AWS: Amazon Web Services

BMC: Business Model Canvas

DCV: Desktop Cloud Visualization (as in NICE DCV, a remote desktop product)

HMD: Head-Mounted Display

LLM: Large Language Model (e.g. ChatGPT)

NDI: Network Device Interface (technology to broadcast MS Teams content)

NPC: Non-Player Character

VR: Virtual Reality

3.4 Reference Documents

See the [References](#) Section included in this document.

3.5 Security issues regarding previous document versions

In response to a revision request from the EU commission, this document no longer includes any credentials to access source code, the learning management system, or Microsoft Teams. Specifically, the following have been removed:

- Username and password for the *e-DIPLOMA Teams moderator account* that was used during the pilots to manage Teams communication. Access to this information by a malicious party could have allowed them to interfere with Teams communications of student participants or reconfigure AI chatbot personas. This is mitigated by the fact that the use of the activity was bound to the EC2 server, which was not and is not accessible to unauthorized people. Access for students is only possible through the e-DIPLOMA Lobby after proper LMS authorization and explicit supervisor assent, where the supervisor herself needs to be authenticated in the LMS. This *e-DIPLOMA Teams moderator account* is no longer necessary. The previously published password was therefore retired. Institutes teaching Prototype 2 Module 3 *Painters* are advised to use their own in-institute Teams subscriptions. Other video chat apps can also be used, with the caveat that support to install the AI chatbot personas is only provided for Teams.
- Usernames for pre-established Teams users, utilized in the pilots for anonymity, were removed. These caused no security issues, but they are no longer needed.
- In the previous version of this document, a fine-grained personal access token was included that gave read-only access to review the project source code on GitHub. This could have caused a minor security issue, as a malevolent party could have accessed the source code, which could have been

used to design attacks using reverse engineering, or, theoretically, to re-create the entire e-DIPLOMA platform using the source code and the documentation. However, the access token had a pre-set expiry date of 2025-03-01, and it was never used before that date. The token is now deleted, so that it is never re-generated by mistake.

- Moodle LMS student and teacher accounts were provided for reviewer access. These allowed user access to specific demonstration courses with clearly delimited authorizations. However, as teachers can manage cloud resources, such an account could be used to allocate cloud servers causing elevated operation costs. These accounts have been terminated on the e-DIPLOMA Moodle server.

Please note that none of the above security issues could have allowed unauthorized people to access sensitive information, including:

- student names,
- student data,
- pilot study participants, or
- measurement data,

as these are either not stored at all (because of anonymization), or stored in secure storage isolated from the above systems. Questionnaire data could have been exposed on Moodle via the teacher accounts provided, but those accounts were never authorized to access the courses instrumented for piloting.

Any party who needs to have legitimate access to the e-DIPLOMA Moodle server or the GitHub code repositories is advised to apply for such access at the respective administrators of those systems. Details are given in Chapter 7.

4 Prototypes overview

4.1 Definitions of terms

activity

An item visible on a Moodle course page, added by a teacher (acting in the role of e-DIPLOMA Course Administrator). e-DIPLOMA activities are a specific type of activity. Clicking such an activity opens an e-DIPLOMA Frontend webpage. e-DIPLOMA activities execute some *learning objects*.

application

A software product available through the e-DIPLOMA platform, which can be used to realise educational materials and activities. There can be multiple *versions* of an application.

client

In a multiuser application, the client is the program that is executed on the user's device, responsible for display and interaction. Clients connect to a *server*.

course

A collection of *learning objects* designed to be studied in succession, teaching some subject.

learning object

A unit of learning material, based on a *version* of an *application*, accompanied with associated *assets*. An activity always concerns a *learning object*.

module

One lesson's worth of learning material. Consists of one or more *learning objects*.

pilot

Pilots measure and document activities using disruptive technologies, in order to arrive at conclusions about their use.

prototype

e-DIPLOMA prototypes are used in the pilots and instrumented to measure and record user characteristics and actions for analysis and research.

server

In a multiuser application, the server is the program that is executed on a dedicated computer, often in the *cloud*. The server is responsible for coherent simulation of virtual reality. *Clients* connect to a server.

version

A specific build of an *application*. *Learning objects* are authored based on a specific application version.

4.2 Proposed prototypes

In this section, we summarize the original prototype concepts as drafted in the Grant Agreement. The Agreement foresaw the implementation of three prototypes. It also prescribed conducting a co-design process, and subsequent redesign to facilitate the goals of the project.

4.2.1 Prototype 1 – Block programming

This course focuses on providing students with basic knowledge of programming and electronics, enabling them to experiment through immersive virtual reality and augmented reality while receiving theoretical lessons via an innovative video format.

The primary objective is to encourage students from any field of study to engage with computer science and develop digital competencies.

The general and specific competencies that students are expected to acquire through this course prototype include the following:

- Knowledge, design, and efficient use of the most appropriate coding structures and commands to solve problems.
- Ability to understand, analyze, and evaluate the structure and architecture of microcontrollers.
- Ability to design and evaluate human-computer interfaces that ensure accessibility and usability.

In terms of learning outcomes, students are expected to:

- Translate basic algorithms expressed in natural language into code, logic, and proper functions.
- Describe the different types of input and output sensors available.
- Explain the main sensor-based interaction techniques.
- Develop basic programs to interact with various types of sensors.

The course curriculum consists of six modules and a final project:

- **Module 1** introduces all theoretical concepts through audiovisual content recorded by the instructor in a three-dimensional environment. The materials used in this lesson will also be used in the subsequent lessons.
- **Module 2** covers general programming concepts, where students engage in block-based programming exercises within a virtual and immersive environment displayed using an HMD.
- **Module 3** introduces the electronics component of the course, allowing students to analyze different sensors through augmented reality, exploring their architecture and applications.
- **Module 4** involves practicing data acquisition from sensors within an immersive virtual reality environment (using HMD).
- **Module 5** focuses on explaining the Arduino microcontroller through augmented reality. This lesson provides students with key information about the microcontroller and how to process inputs and outputs.
- **Module 6** involves solving an exercise where students apply everything they have learned, including programming and assembling sensors and Arduino, within an interactive virtual scenario displayed through HMD.

Finally, the course culminates with a final project titled *Saving the Earth*, in which students collaborate to solve a common objective (such as saving the Amazon, combating a zombie invasion, or addressing global warming) in an immersive virtual reality environment. Students must choose one of the objectives and solve the problem using the programming and electronics knowledge they have acquired.

A visual overview of the proposed course structure is shown in Figure 4.1.

Figure 4.1 Initial prototype proposal

4.2.2 Prototype 2 – Social entrepreneurship

This prototype intends to cover the development and management of social enterprises in an e-learning training course featuring new or disruptive ICT innovations.

The general aim of the course is to create awareness about social economy and social enterprises, appreciate the role of social entrepreneurship that creates social change, deepen participants understanding of the world around them, and to inspire them to create a vision where their passion and desire for change meets self-employability, while testing ICT innovations for e-learning.

Students in this course will gain knowledge about social entrepreneurs and how they are creating solutions to address societal problems, learn how to develop creative solutions to address social problems, and self-empowerment to see social entrepreneurship as a force for social change.

The course is designed for students who want to gain valuable tools to make an impact on the lives of others by setting up, managing and developing a social enterprise.

The course would be divided into 9 Modules and a final project. The theoretical concepts of social entrepreneurship will be presented using virtual online presentations. Interactive videos, documents and podcasts will be elaborated to teach the basic concepts. For the practical concepts, different 3D interactive technologies would be used.

Lecture 1. Set-up a social enterprise

A virtual city with some social problems will be created; the student will be able to move around and visit social companies related to the issue. Information about every company will be shown to the user.

Lecture 2. Circular Human Resources Management

A virtual role-playing game will be developed. Using an HMD, the students will be able to take on different roles in a recruitment process. First, the user puts himself/herself in the shoes of the candidate, a person that suffers social discrimination. And, secondly, the user is the one that hires. The aim of this game is to increase the empathy of the student with the people that usually suffer social problems.

Lecture 3. Circular Financial Management

A mini-game will be developed where the user will have to invest the profits of a company choosing different objectives: own benefit, company benefits or social benefits. The game will show how every decision will affect the society, the city or the environment. The consequences will be determined by the use of AI algorithms.

Lecture 4. Circular Production Management

Augmented reality will be used to design a production chain where the user will have to analyze the benefits of the circular production. Some decisions will have to be taken to enhance the sustainability of the production.

Lecture 5. Circular Marketing Management

The student will have to prepare a virtual presentation of a social enterprise following a commercial aim taking into account ethics, gender, inclusivity, sustainability, etc.

Lecture 6. Circular Communication Relationship Management

A new role-playing game will be created where the student will be immersed in a virtual set using a HMD, and he/she will face different situations. They will have to resolve different types of conflicts between different characters that present personal problems.

Lecture 7. Circular Health and Safety solutions

A videogame will be developed so the user will be able to put into practice the health and safety tips learned in the theoretical part of the course. The safety of the workers of an industry will depend on the decisions taken.

Lecture 8. Circular Environmental Management

An AR game will be developed for increasing the knowledge of the recycling cycle of the waste of an industry. Virtual cards will be designed with information about the recycling process depending on the kind of waste.

Lecture 9. Circular Quality Management

Using Augmented Reality and Virtual Reality, the student will have to make different decisions about the continuation or not of the production despite some defects that appear in some manufactured pieces. Different actions will be offered to the user and the results of everyone will be analyzed.

Finally, the students will face a collaborative global project. Some virtual scenarios visualized by means of HMD will be offered to the students, such as combating global warming or developing a rural or urban area. They will have to choose one of them to show their acquired knowledge setting up a dedicated social enterprise.

4.2.3 Prototype 3 – Virtual Reality in education

This prototype intends to teach and survey the use of VR solutions to inspire use in education. It targets current but also future educators and covers advantages and disadvantages of VR environments. The prototype will address many examples and will actively involve participants. Due to its generality, this prototype intends to be independent of a particular area and will focus on general elements in VR, such as VR technology limitations, interaction, display possibilities, or presence and immersion. Educators and those involved in the production of educational materials are being prepared for VR.

Participants in this course will gain knowledge of VR technology and its possibilities. They will learn to apply VR and become able to judge appropriate options. They will also be able to identify and address common pitfalls in VR and increase their awareness with regards to inherent limitations. They will further develop an understanding of how to design educational material for a virtual reality environment. Furthermore, they will learn about how VR can bring new possibilities to teaching.

The course curriculum consists of six lectures starting with a video and then an HMD experience, as well as a final project (a paper manual in combination with an HMD activity): (below is a shortened overview of the original outline)

Lecture 1: Introduction

Introduction to the virtual environment and basic VR training. The technology is reviewed to give an overview of the limitations of very affordable but widespread devices. Basic representations are covered, including panoramas, 3D movies, or 3D models, and immersive audio.

Lecture 2: Navigation

The session will introduce different standard navigation methods in a virtual-reality environment, such as teleportation, fly-through, or dragging motion. In this context, simulator sickness is addressed and explained.

Lecture 3: Interaction

In this module, some interaction and presentation techniques are covered. Starting with the standard integration of augmented-reality and controller-based interaction. Finally, advanced topics are presented as an outlook covering haptic devices and their limitations.

Lecture 4: Visualization

While part of the original intent, VR is no longer restricted to reproducing the real world in every aspect. For educational purposes, many times abstractions and simplifications are more effective. This lecture

teaches different solutions and shows use cases illustrating the underlying potential for their use in VR. To understand these aspects, perceptual properties of the human visual system will be linked to concrete examples.

Lecture 5: Collaboration and group work

VR makes different collaboration modalities possible. Virtual collaboration, collocation and interaction are examined. In this context, attention will also be placed on virtual avatars.

Lecture 6: Advanced aspects

VR offers creative use cases that exceed possibilities in real-life demonstrations. This lecture dives into several examples, e.g., exploration in time and space, where events can be slowed down and analyzed from different viewpoints, or the use of scale to illustrate the impact of small on large processes seamlessly.

The final activity is the design of a virtual museum. The participants of the course can design the layout and appearance of the environment, integrate objects as art (or educational) pieces, influence illumination and visualization, and highlight important points that can be linked to trigger mechanisms to guide the focus of the students, who can experience the museum afterwards -the resulting virtual museums can be shared. The designs can be stored to continue the creation at a latter point, or to make it available on the platform in the future.

4.3 Final prototypes

In this section we describe the redesigned prototypes that emerged after the co-creation process. In general, these consist of more focused activities allowing assessment of the impact of specific educational approaches and technologies.

The number of modules in a prototype, and the duration of the respective activities, was limited by the time and resources allocated for the pilot study in the proposal and the grant agreement. **D5.2 Definition of appropriate metrics for the assessment of learning competencies** established guidelines. Following those, together with pre- and post-activity measurements, one sitting for students should not take more than 90 minutes to avoid fatigue. An experiment cycle at one location with a foreseen count of 50 participants must fit into one or two weeks, because special equipment might need to be transported. The final versions of the prototypes have been designed to meet those constraints, while keeping the essential functional elements of the original concepts.

4.3.1 Prototype 1 – Block programming

After conducting various co-design activities (weekly meetings, focus groups, and a hackathon) with key project stakeholders, including students, families, developers, and teachers/professors, changes were made to the course modules.

The results of these activities indicated that the prototype should offer a shorter experience and require fewer technology transitions. Consequently, it was decided to group together the modules with similar educational content and those that used the same technology.

Following these adjustments, the course currently consists of four modules while retaining the final project, as outlined below (see Figure 4.2), and preserving the initial learning objective. The prototype alternates between theory-based modules and practical modules, using either immersive virtual reality or augmented reality.

- **Module 1** introduces theoretical concepts via audiovisual content on general programming topics, which will be practiced in the following module.
- **Module 2** features an interactive activity with practical block-based programming exercises in an immersive virtual environment using a Head-Mounted Display (HMD).
- **Module 3** presents theoretical concepts via audiovisual content on the basics of electronics: the Arduino board, sensors, actuators, and how they are assembled.
- **Module 4** uses augmented reality to identify the various devices covered in the course, display key information about them, and allow students to complete exercises related to their connections and communication.

Finally, the course retains the final project titled *Saving the Earth*. In pairs, within an immersive virtual reality environment using HMD, students collaborate to achieve a common objective by applying the knowledge they have gained in electronics and programming.

More detailed information about each module can be found in Chapter 6 of the document.

Figure 4.2 Changes made to the prototype 1

4.3.2 Prototype 2 – Social entrepreneurship

The co-design phase revealed that the original concept was too extensive to serve as a feasible pilot where the impact of different technologies could be studied. Instead, the most practical elements of the concept — amenable to a learning-by-doing approach — were compiled into a course consisting of five modules, each of them featuring a unique setup with different student group dynamics and disruptive techniques. Lessons lacking a unique connection to the social enterprise aspect (i.e. quality control, workplace safety) do not appear as individual modules. A decision was also made to de-emphasize the ubiquitous “circular”

aspect that had somewhat nebulous connections to e.g. human resource management, and handle environmental aspects as one of the facets of social impact that these enterprises generate.

4.3.2.1 Module 1 *Lodestars*: The Social Enterprise and the Social Entrepreneur

This module is a group activity featuring *exploration*, based on the original concept of Lecture 1 in the proposal. A virtual city with some social problems is shown in Virtual Reality; where a student wearing an HMD can visit characters representing some social enterprise or a related or contrastable entity. Instead of just showing information about every company to the user, the student must talk to the characters, using AI-based speech-to-text recognition and an AI-based chat. Characters have well-defined relations, and an investigation must be conducted to reveal more characters and social issues. While only a single student enters the VR, all students need to work as a group to discuss and analyze the entities they encountered, and classify them as social enterprises, profit-oriented enterprises, social services, consumers, or criminals, following the provided criteria. The activity aims to achieve higher objectives on the Bloom taxonomy up to the level of Analysis [1].

4.3.2.2 Module 2 *Heroes*: Urban Management for Social Outcomes

This module is a 4-user *cooperative* gaming experience. It takes the concept of Lecture 2 from the proposal to demonstrate the social impact of financial decisions. However, students do not play as individual entrepreneurs managing company goals, but as policymakers in a city, to explore the larger scale interplay between Housing, Industry, Food Supply, Health, and Entertainment. The virtual city is simulated to show these aspects, and imbalances resulting in social problems in one of these areas impact city population, which the student must try to avoid. They must reach at least a partial consensus on the course of action, by indicating their proposals in the VR environment, and supporting proposals by their peers.

4.3.2.3 Module 3 *Painters*: Business Model Canvas for a Social Enterprise

This module gathers all aspects of social business design mentioned in the proposal into a team *co-design* activity using the Business Model Canvas (BMC). Novel aspects of this activity include:

- communication through videoconferencing (Microsoft Teams)
- AI chatbot personas that can be interviewed to explore the social problem that an energy sharing enterprise can solve (integrated into Teams)
- 3D shared environment for canvas manipulation (Brainstorm's Edison, with Teams integrated)

4.3.2.4 Module 4 *Allies*: Human Resources and Team Management at a Social Company

This module takes the concepts of Lecture 2 (HR) and Lecture 6 (communications, team management) and realizes them as learning-by-doing activities in a *single player* computer game, with AI chatbots. The chatbots play potential employees, who can be interviewed, and then assigned roles in the social enterprise managed by the student, which is modelled after the Estonian recycling shop company Sõbralt Sõbrale [2]. Success depends on probing the relevant characteristics of the interviewees, assembling a team that covers all responsibilities, and resolving conflicts emerging within the team.

4.3.2.5 Module 5 *Angels*: Marketing of Social Products and Services

This module takes Lectures 4 and 5 from the proposal to realize a *competitive* educational game played by four students. While students can, and should focus on building their own enterprise, keeping an eye on other player's activities can offer important clues, and the opportunity to avoid competition, or initiate

it by entering the same lucrative market. The game is a card game, where financing, market research, products, services, promotions are all represented by cards not only imparting knowledge, but also the associated mechanisms.

4.3.3 Prototype 3 – Virtual Reality in education

During the co-design stage, important decisions have been taken with regards to pilot design. The focus was placed on the interactive parts of the navigation and interaction lectures to make them the centerpiece of attention. As they convey fundamental information about the use of VR, they were identified as crucial introductory components for educators without VR experience. Additionally, one developed application for holonomy navigation (a mathematical concept) was deemed too abstract for the prototype but will be investigated in independent case studies.

The course was still completed to address all topics. Further, many of the activities directly connect to planned user studies to identify best practices that can help others in the future. With regards to the course content, it covers all six topics that have been outlined in the proposal. After the introduction, each of the remaining 5 lectures is supported by a practical part, in which one or several HMD activities allow the user to experience elements of the previous lecture. In total, 17 such interactive activities have been designed for the HMD, plus a complex concluding VR application that combines all topics in a final activity. The result of the final activity are virtual spaces that users can share for others to experience, e.g., via the e-DIPLOMA platform.

All HMD learning activities have been integrated into a single program that enables access to the different stages directly from the main menu.

- Lecture 1: Introduction to VR (video)
- Lecture 2: Interaction (video + HMD applications 1-6)
- Lecture 3: Navigation (video + HMD applications 7-10)
- Lecture 4: Visualization (video + HMD applications 11-12)
- Lecture 5: Collaboration (video + HMD application 13-15)
- Lecture 6: Demonstration - Advanced VR use (video + HMD application 16)
- Final project (VR-Education Scene Editor - application 17)

5 e-DIPLOMA Server Toolset

5.1 Toolset purpose

Deploying a multiplayer application to the e-DIPLOMA Platform requires creating both a Windows client build, and a Linux dedicated server build of the application. Since the platform uses the Amazon GameLift service for hosting dedicated servers, it is essential to properly integrate the GameLift SDK and the AWS SDK into the dedicated server component of any multiplayer application. However, this task may present several challenges. As part of the project, the e-DIPLOMA Server Toolset was created, consisting of various tools that simplify the integration process for application developers.

5.2 e-DIPLOMA Server Local Test Tool

This command-line tool allows developers to test the multiplayer application and the GameLift integration locally, revealing any potential errors before deploying the application to the e-DIPLOMA Platform. By issuing a single command, developers can automatically launch the dedicated server build and multiple instances of the client build on their computer, enabling testing with one or more clients in a local Windows environment. Multiplayer VR applications are supported as well. The tool requires the following dependencies to function properly:

- GameLift Local service: A command-line tool developed by Amazon that allows running a limited version of the GameLift service locally and testing integration against it.
- AWS CLI: For sending requests to the GameLift Local service.
- Windows Subsystem for Linux: For running Linux dedicated server builds on Windows.

Figure 5.1 illustrates how the e-DIPLOMA Server Local Test Tool launches the multiplayer application locally.

Figure 5.1 Launching the multiplayer application locally

5.3 e-DIPLOMA Server Unity Package

The e-DIPLOMA Server Unity Package simplifies the integration of the GameLift SDK and the AWS SDK for multiplayer Unity applications by providing an API through which interactions between the application and the Amazon GameLift service can be managed more easily. The package can be installed from a private GitHub repository managed by BME, using the Unity Package Manager. In addition to standard build testing with the e-DIPLOMA Server Local Test Tool, the package supports testing the integration directly inside the Unity Editor. This enables faster iterations during development, as there is no need to rebuild the application to test changes. When testing inside the editor, the package uses the AWS CLI to communicate with the GameLift Local service running in the background.

5.4 e-DIPLOMA Unity Sample Project

This sample project demonstrates how to integrate the e-DIPLOMA Server Unity Package into non-VR multiplayer Unity applications. It uses Photon Fusion 2 for multiplayer networking. In the project, each player controls a cube and observes the scene from a top-down view (see Figure 5.2). A timer in the top-left corner displays the remaining time of the multiplayer session. The project also illustrates how to test package integration within the Unity Editor by using the Multi-Peer Mode of Photon Fusion 2. This mode enables simulating both a server and multiple clients within the editor. The number of clients and the multiplayer session duration can be configured in the project. Once the simulation starts, the user can switch between clients and decide which one to control.

Figure 5.2 The e-DIPLOMA Unity Sample Project

5.5e-DIPLOMA Unity VR Sample Project

This sample project serves as a base for multiplayer Unity VR applications integrated with the e-DIPLOMA Server Unity Package. It is built on top of the Photon Fusion 2 VR Host sample project. Each player controls a VR avatar and can interact with grabbable objects which are synchronized over the network (see Figure 5.3). The remaining time of the session is displayed on a board in the scene. This project also supports testing inside the Unity Editor by leveraging the Multi-Peer Mode, which simulates a server and multiple VR clients. The user can switch between VR clients during the simulation via a tab and can also choose to observe the scene from the perspective of a different client, other than the one they control, which can be useful for testing multiplayer mechanics within the editor.

Figure 5.3 The e-DIPLOMA Unity VR Sample Project

6 Module documentation

In this section we document the individual demonstrators for the modules of each prototype. The purpose of this documentation is to facilitate the evaluation of these modules as a demonstrator deliverable and to act as an extended version of the user manual for engaging them in pilots or other educational activities. This does not include documentation for developers, the full educational material, or study protocols. Nevertheless, relevant data capture capabilities of the modules are documented.

P1. Block programming

P1M1. Basis of Programming

P1M1 1 General Description

This module consists of audiovisual content distributed over four videos covering the fundamental concepts of programming. This content, made with the Edison tool, has been designed to provide an introductory foundation for preparing students for the practical activities in the second module.

P1M1 2 Activity Flow

The module is divided into **four videos**, each lasting approximately 1 to 3 minutes. The course adopts a visual programming approach, where programming is done by manipulating graphics blocks that fit together like puzzle pieces. Block programming is presented as a great option for introducing programming to beginners of all ages, helping them develop essential **programming competencies**.

In the first video titled *What's Programming All About?*, the concept of programming is explained in general terms, along with the approach that will be used throughout the course. Specifically, this first video illustrates what programming is, the importance of sequentiality in code and the programming language that will be used along the course.

The second video (*Loops: The Repeaters of Coding*) and third video (*The conditional: Making Decisions in Code*) introduce common control structures in programming, such as loops and conditional statements. In the case of loops, the video teaches the repetition of instructions using the "for" loop. For conditionals, it shows how to make decisions based on whether a condition is true or false using the "if" statement.

This module finishes with the fourth video (*Integrating What We Have Learned so Far*) in which an example is provided where the previously covered concepts are integrated, and a block program's execution is broken down step by step. This video prepares students more concretely for the practical exercises they find in the next module.

P1M1 3 User Actions

In this module, the user experience is based on watching the four theoretical videos. The first and last videos must be watched in the same order, but the videos about loops and conditionals can be watched interchangeably.

P1M1 3.1 Requirements

All videos can be accessed through links on the Moodle page of the e-DIPLOMA platform. This module is available from any computer or smartphone with an internet connection.

P1M1 4 Screenshots and Visuals

Figure P1M1.1, Figure P1M1.2, Figure P1M1.3, and Figure P1M1.4 show screenshots of the content of this module.

Figure P1M1.1 A frame from video "What is Programming All About?"

Figure P1M1.2 A frame from video "Loops: The Repeaters of Coding"

Figure P1M1.3 A frame from video "The conditional: Making Decisions in Code"

Figure P1M1.4 A frame from video "Integrating What We Have Learned so Far"

P1M2. Virtual Playground: Explore Block Coding in Virtual Reality

P1M2 1 General Description

This module consists of an interactive experience in an immersive virtual reality environment. It proposes various challenges that require the application of fundamental **programming competencies** to solve them. Through this engaging and hands-on approach, students practice all the concepts covered in Module 1.

P1M2 2 Activity Flow

Virtual Playground: Explore Block Coding in Virtual Reality represents 6 exercises to be solved through block programming. The objective in each exercise is to program the behavior of a robot based on an Arduino system that must reach the plants in an environment composed of cubes to capture their humidity. The proposed exercises are of increasing and incremental difficulty. Figure P1M2.5 shows what this module looks like and indicates all the elements of which this experience is composed.

Figure P1M2.5

Elements of the module 2

At the beginning of the experience, the student has the possibility to access two tutorials. One of them, *Controls tutorial*, prepares the student to get familiarized with the controls through an interactive manner. The *Dynamics tutorial* explains the rules of the exercises interactively.

After completing the tutorials, the students must solve the exercises dragging and dropping blocks that represent code instructions under the block “START”. The student has to correctly complete the current exercise to move on to the next one. To solve each of the exercises, the student has specific instructions available to compose their code, which increase according to the difficulty of the exercise. Each exercise is designed so that only one correct solution is possible.

The first exercise focuses on practicing fundamental concepts of programming such as the order of the execution of instructions. Moreover, this exercise allows students to get familiarized with the environment, with block-based programming and gain an overview of the broader context for subsequent exercises.

The second exercise incorporates the requirement to use different instructions, introducing a slightly higher level of difficulty. This way, students are challenged to expand their understanding and proficiency with new programming commands. By doing so, it not only reinforces the concepts of sequential programming but also facilitates the acquisition of additional knowledge about various instructions.

Exercise 3 introduces the concept of loops. At this stage, students are required to solve the first proposed exercise using a loop, understanding the operation and advantages of using this control statement.

Exercise 4 encompasses all the elements covered previously, including sequential execution and loops, and introduces the conditional control structure.

In the fifth and sixth exercises, new concepts are not introduced, but they require students to delve deeper into making more complex code using loops and conditionals. These exercises are designed to push students beyond basic instruction usage, encouraging them to explore more complex solutions. Through these exercises, students will not only solidify their understanding of fundamental programming concepts but also enhance their ability to manage and organize code more effectively and refine problem-solving competencies.

At the end of each exercise, students obtain the time in which they have completed the current exercise. Additionally, when students make a mistake in the code of any exercise, the system provides feedback for them to revise the code. Figure P1M2.6 represents the activity flow.

Figure P1M2.6 Activity flow diagram of Module 2

P1M2 3 User Actions

In this module, users can interact with the environment and perform various actions using the following controls:

- Teleportation: Move to different locations within the virtual environment by pointing at the floor and pressing "Grip Button".
- Grabbing Objects: Drag and drop programming blocks by holding down the "Grip Button".
- Remove Objects: Reset the position of a block by holding down the button "A Button"
- Interaction with buttons: Press buttons or interact with UI elements in the virtual interface by pointing at them and pressing the "Trigger".
- Zooming Objects: Bring closer or move programming blocks away from user's point of view by moving the right joystick
- Rotating View: Rotate the user's point of view without physically turning by moving the left joystick.

Figure P1M2.7 represents the controllers and actions.

Figure P1M2.7 Controls and actions of Module 2

P1M2 3.1 Requirements

All videos can be accessed through links on the Moodle page of the e-DIPLOMA platform. This module is available from any computer or smartphone with an internet connection.

Figure P1M2.8 Interaction of Module 2

P1M3. Basis of Electronics

P1M3 1 General description

Same as the first module of the course, this module consists of audiovisual content made with Edison ecosystem. This module prepares the students to **understand key concepts** of microcontroller programming, sensors and actuators. To produce these videos, 3D objects with animations from Module 4 are used to support the explanations. In addition, Edison features have been used to create a more engaging experience.

P1M3 2 Activity Flow

This module is divided into **two videos** of about 2 minutes each. The first video titled *First Steps into the World of Electronics* explains what an Arduino board is and the role of sensors and actuators. As examples of sensors, ultrasonic and humidity sensors are presented. Additionally, actuators are exemplified by servo-driven wheels and LEDs. These sensors and actuators together with the Arduino board form the system on which the robot car that the student has programmed in module 2 is based. The blocks of movement, obstacle detection and humidity measurement are instructions that are related to the functionality of this system.

The second video called *Connecting Arduino, Sensors, and Actuators* explains the assembly of an Arduino system and how it works. It also presents an additional board that facilitates the connection of the components and that will be used in the subsequent modules. The video ends with an example of the behavior of the robot car relating the programming modules to the electronics modules.

P1M3 3 User Actions

In this module, there is no interaction as it consists of watching videos explaining theoretical concepts that support the practice in the next module.

P1M3 4 Requirements

All videos can be accessed through links on the Moodle page of the e-DIPLOMA platform. This module is available from any computer or smartphone with an internet connection.

P1M3 5 Screenshots and Visuals

Figure P1M3.9 and Figure P1M3.10 show screenshots of the content of this module.

Figure P1M3.9 A frame from video "First Steps into the World of Electronics"

Figure P1M3.10 A frame from video "Connecting Arduino, Sensors, and Actuators"

P1M4. ARduino Learn: Practice with Microcontroller and Components

P1M4 1 General description

This module is based on an Augmented Reality application which is designed to learn electronic components and their assembly. In this module, students will learn in greater depth what was covered in the previous module by expanding on the actual components along with an interactive activity.

P1M4 2 Activity Flow

ARduino Learn is designed to teach information about the components of Arduino UNO board, Arduino shield V2, Grove ultrasonic Ranger V2.0 sensor, and DHT11 V1.2 humidity and temperature sensor.

When the application starts, a main menu is shown. Three options are available: Start, Instructions, Settings, and Exit. Start option takes the user directly into the interactive activities. The instructions option displays an overview of how the application works and how to navigate the interface. The settings option allows you to change the language of the application. Finally, the Exit option closes the app. Figure P1M4.11 shows a screenshot of the main menu.

Figure P1M4.11 Main menu of *ARduino Learn*

The application includes two main modes. The learning mode is to explore theoretical information over real components. In this mode, the student must point at the actual components using the device's camera. The application overlays detailed information about the parts of each component. In this mode,

there is a “Play” button that starts an interactive activity where the user must select and place the names of each component part in its corresponding description.

Figure P1M4.12 Learning mode exploratory phase of ARduino Learn

When the name of that component is placed, it becomes transparent, and the corresponding component part is colored in purple. Selected parts are highlighted in blue and components with the name already assigned appear in grey. The student can end the game by pressing the “Finish” button, at which point the results are displayed indicating how many assignments were correct.

Figure P1M4.13 Interactive activity in learning mode of ARduino Learn

In the practice mode, the student must use the print template to correctly locate the components (see Figure P1M4.14).

Figure P1M4.14 Paper template and the correct component locations

During this interactive practice, the student will learn how to assemble an Arduino shield with sensors using the Grove connectors. This process is carried out by touching the sensor and then the port on the base shield where it is to be connected. It is important to know that the sensors must connect to digital ports according to what was learned in the previous mode.

Not all connections are allowed; for example, two sensors cannot be connected to the same port on the base shield. If the connections are correct, a message will appear confirming this.

Additionally, there is a button that allows the student to disconnect every cable at the same time if needed. Figure P1M4.15 shows what this mode of practice looks like.

Figure P1M4.15 Practice mode of ARduino Learn

The complete flow of this activity is depicted in the diagram in Figure P1M4.16.

Figure P1M4.16 Activity flow diagram of Module 4

P1M4 3 User Actions

In this module, the main interaction is touching the screen of the smartphone or tablet. For the learning mode, the student must focus on each physical component with the smartphone or tablet camera. For the practice mode, the student must place each component in the correct place on the printed template and focus on it with the camera.

P1M4 4 Requirements

To effectively run and install this module a smartphone or tablet with Android Operating System is required. It must be capable of running AR applications with an integrated camera. It is recommended that the Android version is 7.0 or higher. It is necessary to allow the installation of applications from unknown sources. If this is not possible, it is necessary to change the device settings.

Additionally, a print template is needed to activate the 3D models in practice mode. Moreover, the following physical electronics components are necessary: Arduino UNO Shield, Base Shield V2, Grove Ultrasonic Ranger V2.0 sensor, and DHT11 V1.2 temperature and humidity sensor.

P1M4 5 Screenshots and Visuals

Figure P1M4.17 Interaction in Module 4 learning mode

Figure P1M4.18 Setup for practice mode

Figure P1M4.19 Interaction in Module 4 practice mode

P1M5. Collaborative Virtual Reality Codeventure

P1M5 1 General Description

This final module is a **collaborative** activity in an immersive virtual reality environment for two participants. The activity takes place in a setting already familiar to students from Module 2. The robot car, which was programmed in Module 2 and whose components were detailed in Module 4, is reintroduced here, with its assembly serving as a preliminary step to programming. In this way, the module functions as a culminating activity that integrates both **programming** and **electronics**, reinforcing the competencies developed throughout the course.

P1M5 2 Activity Flow

To launch this collaborative activity, both students must have the game running. At the beginning of the activity, they are prompted to select a mission from "Save the Amazon", "Reduce Climate Change" or "Avoid the Zombie Attack" (see Figure P1M5.20).

Figure P1M5.20 Main menu of Module 5

Both participants must choose the same mission. Once the mission is selected, they will assemble the robot car, which will then be programmed to achieve the chosen objective (see Figure P1M5.21).

Figure P1M5.21 Assembly of the robot car components

The robot car used in this module is the same one programmed in Module 2, controlled by an Arduino system covered in Modules 3 and 4. Whether the mission can be successfully completed depends on the sensors installed on the car. For example, if students select the "Save the Amazon" mission, where the goal is to monitor plant humidity, the robot car must be equipped with an ultrasonic sensor to detect obstacles and avoid collisions as it moves through the environment, as well as a DHT11 sensor to gather data on plant humidity.

When both students have assembled their robot cars, the programming phase begins. In this stage, the robot cars must navigate the same environment and cooperate to reach the goal in the fewest possible rounds. Figure P1M5.22 shows the map of the environment. A round consists of programming the robots and then executing that program for each robot car.

Figure P1M5.22 Scenario map

Each mission has a different objective. For the "Save the Amazon" mission, it is essential to monitor the humidity levels of all plants. To complete the "Avoid the Zombie Attack" mission, the entire environment must be enclosed by activating buttons that raise the walls. Finally, in the "Reduce Climate Change" mission, all trash scattered across the environment must be collected.

Achieving the objective requires careful planning of movements to access initially unreachable areas. As the students progress through the mission, they are rewarded by unlocking new instructions they can integrate into their code, allowing them to accomplish the goal more efficiently.

Figure P1M5.23 represents the activity flow of this module.

Figure P1M5.23 Activity flow diagram of Module 5

P1M5 3 User Actions

In this module, users can interact with the environment and perform various actions using the following controls:

- Teleportation: Move to different locations within the virtual environment by pointing at the floor and pressing “Grip Button”.
- Grabbing Objects: Drag and drop programming blocks and car components by holding down the “Grip Button”.
- Remove Objects: Reset the position of a block by holding down the button “A Button”
- Interaction with buttons: Press buttons or interact with UI elements in the virtual interface by pointing at them and pressing the “Trigger”.
- Zooming Objects: Bring closer or move programming blocks away from user’s point of view by moving the right joystick
- Rotating View: Rotate the user’s point of view without physically turning by moving the left joystick.

P1M5 4 Requirements

For this module to work effectively and the two users to participate simultaneously, equipment with the following features is necessary:

Computer with Windows 10/11 Operating System:

Processor: Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-9700 CPU @ 3.00GHz, 3000 Mhz, 8 core processors, 8 logical processors
RAM: 16.0 GB

Graphics card: NVIDIA GeForce RTX 2060

Storage: 0.5 GB available

HP Omnicept Reverb g2 with controllers or Oculus Meta Quest 2/ 3 with controllers.

P1M5 5 Screenshots and visuals

Figure P1M5.24 Setup of Module 5

Figure P1M5.25 Main Virtual environment of Module 5

P2. Social Entrepreneurship

P2M1.Lodestars – The Social Entrepreneur

P2M1 1 Module realization

P2M1 1.1 Learning material

The module introduces social entrepreneurship, through examples, as contrasted with regular enterprises that lack a social focus, social services that lack an entrepreneurial component, and other activities like communal services, crime, or consumption.

The module aims to teach students about the various ways one can be a social entrepreneur, how they can help different communities and social classes in need, while maintaining a tenable business operation. Instead of presenting the classic examples in non-interactive descriptions, students can explore a city, talking to real social entrepreneurs, or at least virtual ones, who know the aspects of their respective activities, and can share their knowledge and ambition. Students must apply critical thinking, as not all characters they can talk to are exemplary social entrepreneurs, or even morally right.

P2M1 1.2 Educational material

To realize the goals discussed previously, an application for virtual reality was created, where the players can talk to virtual social entrepreneurs, discuss their experiences, ambitions, and learn about the topic in an immersive manner. These characters are controlled by an AI chat model, making them able to respond beyond simple pre-defined answers, behaving as a real person would. These non-Player Characters (hereby shortened to “NPC”) contain a unique description about different social entrepreneur jobs and their businesses. These are based on real world examples of social enterprises. Figure P2M1.26 shows a conversation with “Martin”, a small-scale farmer. The player can talk through the microphone and the AI answers through spoken audio.

Figure P2M1.26 An example conversation

The game itself is played by multiple people, each taking turns venturing into the virtual world and speaking with some of the many different characters, after which they return to their groups to discuss the conversations they just had. This approach means that everyone in the group is involved in the discussion, not just the person who actually spoke to the characters. So, instead of repeating conversations for each player and having every player speak to each character, we require group work and discussion. The stated task of the players is to identify as many genuine social entrepreneurs as possible.

The game, besides social entrepreneurs, also contains other types of characters, like criminals, regular social workers, plain old-school for-profit businesses, and customers. There is no in-game element in which the player would have to decide if the person they spoke to was a social entrepreneur or not. Instead, the classification is left to group discussion, meaning everyone can take part in the decision, sharing their experiences and opinions about the topic.

Figure P2M1.27 Example of a non-social entrepreneur NPC

The descriptions for the different social entrepreneur characters, and by extension the teaching material itself, is very easily extendable with additional subjects, since it is implemented in a way that we can simply add newer characters representing new jobs and personalities, thus adding a whole palette of new topics to talk about and learn. Figure P2M1.28 shows the *platform template* in the Unity editor, which is easily reusable for creating new characters. This single object type contains everything needed to create NPCs with their own personality and place them in the city.

Figure P2M1.28 The interface for learning material developers for creating NPCs

P2M1 1.2.1 Gameplay outline

In the beginning of the game, players find themselves in front of a miniature model of a city. There, they can choose between pinpoints (like in popular navigation software), each of which teleports them to a different NPC in the big, life-sized city where they can have conversations with the social entrepreneur characters. After the conversation ends, the players are teleported back to the mockup, where they can select another individual to talk to. Figure P2M1.29 shows the city mockup on which the player can select the next character by clicking on a pin. White pins were already visited. The mockup is the exact, miniature copy of the big city.

Figure P2M1.29 City navigation

P2M1 1.2.2 VR Experience

In the co-creation phase, the possibility of free VR exploration was discarded, as it led to dizziness or nausea, while it was neither necessary nor beneficial in contacting the relevant NPCs. As a result, the open world solution (see Figure P2M1.30) has been modified to limit motion in VR to teleporting to locations where the NPCs can be engaged.

Previously, players could walk across the whole city, and visit NPCs, cars and buildings anywhere. This could have given more opportunities for later game updates, but according to feedback, it is not working well with the VR environment, because players may easily find themselves in unwanted situations or feel sick. In the final version, players are instantly teleported to the fixed area of the NPC they chose on the mockup, and they cannot move away from there. This helps in coordinating the gameplay and avoid unforeseen scenarios.

Figure P2M1.30 Free flight view

Figure P2M1.31 Jump-to-scene view

Figure P2M1.32 Random exploration

Figure P2M1.33 Player directly teleported to talk to NPC

P2M1 2 Requirement Specification

P2M1 2.1 Goals

P2M1 2.1.1 Ease of use and accessibility

The most important goal when designing the module was ease of usability and accessibility, meaning that anyone should be able to play the game and learn the lessons it teaches, without the need of any kind of training or specialized knowledge beforehand. This is to ensure classes can proceed smoothly without any extensive training, tutorial, or extensive manual reading sessions, and to also potentially expand the group of students who can benefit from the module. This means people with disabilities, or just lacking in general knowledge of technology, especially the likes of Virtual Reality.

P2M1 2.1.2 Immersion and teaching effectiveness

Another important factor is immersion and leveraging the benefits of technology which are not present during regular teaching. If our students are more immersed in the virtual world which we make, they will pay more attention, therefore they will be learning more effectively. Thus, it is also vital to make the experience interesting for the course participants, by making the world which the module takes place in worthwhile to take part in and use the “wow-factor” of virtual reality by taking advantage of the unique properties of the medium.

P2M1 2.2 User actions

The module does not assume any kind of technical or technology related skills from the students, neither does it aim to teach any of these. Therefore, the game does not contain mechanics that require dexterity or complex user input.

The only assumption made about the user is that they can speak English or Italian. Support for other languages can be added if the speech-to-text, LLM, and text-to-speech modules support that language.

Users have two main ways of interacting with the virtual world:

1. They should be able to explore the virtual world and move around in it and choose which AI NPC they wish to speak to.
2. After choosing, they should be able to have a conversation with said NPC and ask them questions freely, albeit in a limited fashion.

P2M1 2.2.1 Exploration

To reduce the dizziness caused by moving around in virtual reality, teleportation should be preferred over flying or walking in the virtual environment, however the player physically walking around in the classroom should be accounted for by giving the player space to walk around in the teleportation areas.

To facilitate this, the player should not be required to move around in the city, but should be provided with a bird's eye view of the town and be able to see potential points of interest (i.e. AI NPCs to speak to) by easy to recognize markers such as pins used in popular navigation software (see image below).

Figure P2M1.34 Concept art for bird's eye view when exploring the city

In the above image yet-to-be-explored points of interest are shown with a red marker, while the white marker points to an area which has already been visited.

P2M1 2.2.2 Speaking to AI NPCs

Communication with the citizens of the virtual world should be achieved by speaking plain English (or an appropriate other supported language, notably Italian and Spanish), utilizing the microphone of the Virtual Reality headset. The user should ask questions about the person they are speaking to, to learn more information about them, and ultimately about social entrepreneurship. The characters should not be too talkative though, forcing the player to engage more with them by asking more questions, and not getting long lectures, which would make the game less engaging.

Conversations should be limited in time however, to ensure the full playthrough of the module can fit in a single lesson during teaching. Once the timer expires, players should be teleported back to the previous bird's eye view section and be able to choose another character to speak to.

P2M1 2.3 Mechanisms

P2M1 2.3.1 Making a living world

To make the world more immersive for the players, the virtual city should include small details to make it more believable and catch the attention of course participants, to ensure deeper learning.

These should include citizens and vehicles roaming the streets, diverse buildings and various decorations.

P2M1 2.3.2 Relaying information to the player

Since we cannot assume the player knows any “gaming” terms or conventions, it is imperative that the game state is always communicated towards the player. This should be achieved with appropriate icons, sound cues, etc.

Text in the game should be tailored towards a more general audience, so it is more easily picked up.

P2M1 2.3.3 Collecting data during the lecture

Data should be collected in the VR game to track player progress and assess understanding of educational content. By analyzing player behavior, engagement, and performance, we can identify areas where learners may struggle and adjust the game accordingly. Additionally, this data helps improve the game's design, ensuring it meets educational objectives effectively while enhancing the learning experience.

To this end, the following data is collected:

- Data captured by the VR headset
- Data provided by the Emotibit equipment
- Logs about actions the player performed

P2M1 3 Technical background

P2M1 3.1 Artificial Intelligence

At the core of this module lie multiple artificial intelligence models. Achieving conversations is a complicated multi-step process, which consists of transcribing what the player says (speech to text), formulating an answer (conversations), and finally playing the audio for said answer in the voice of the character (text to speech). To perform these steps, we decided to use AI models which are capable of these tasks, but to arrive at the models we finally chose we had to experiment and choose the ones that were up to the tasks.

Figure P2M1.35 High level overview of the conversational pipeline

P2M1 3.1.1 Transcription AI

For our speech-to-text solution, we experimented with multiple technologies. Our first choice was the solution given by the Windows Speech Recognition API. This technology was found to be wholly incompatible with VR, as sometimes the transcription would break when the players took off the VR headset to pass it to the next player, and no text would be returned.

After this we decided to move on to test another technology, provided yet again by Microsoft, called the Mixed Reality Toolkit, which is developed to be used specifically in games. The same issue came up however, because under the hood this toolkit uses the same Windows Speech Recognition API, which we later came to learn.

Both of these previous solutions performed the calculations remotely on Microsoft servers, which was advantageous, since it would minimize the hardware requirements of the game, but since neither proved to suit our goals, we decided to try out OpenAI's Whisper model. This is a free to use model which can be run locally, with different sizes which trade transcription precision for more computing power needed. We decided to use one of the smaller models, to keep the previously mentioned computing load to a minimum. This approach proved to be effective enough during development, only a bit slow, as the transcription would take between 5 to 10 seconds, taking most of the answer round-time. When we performed actual testing on the hardware on which the lectures would be held, it proved to be excruciatingly slow, as the answers were now up to half a minute and over. We found the previous times manageable, as these are

the restrictions when running such models on a local machine instead of a central computational server, but these actual times were simply unusable.

Finally, we decided to move to a dedicated service called AWS Transcribe, provided by Amazon. This was yet another external solution, but this proved to be the most capable approach of the previously tried ones, effectively allowing real-time transcriptions with minimal delay, under half a second, while still being very accurate about pronounced text transcriptions. In the end this was the one technology we decided to stick with, as it was most suitable for our task.

P2M1 3.1.2 Conversational AI

After transcribing the questions spoken by the player, we must generate an answer which could be spoken by the virtual character the user is speaking to. To achieve this, the first version of the game used a smaller model named *Alpaca 7b*, which could be run locally at our university. This, however, was not sufficient, as the task proved to be too complex for it: NPCs did not understand their roles, and would often confuse the player and themselves, answering in the third person.

We upgraded the model to a bigger and more powerful one, called *Llama 3* (the previous one used was an offshoot of the *Llama 2* model). This model was smart enough to perform its task correctly, as the characters could now always focus conversations on their job, even if the player tried to divert the subject. This model is sufficient for the project's educational purposes, but further changes could still upgrade the quality of the communication skills of the virtual characters.

Alongside this in-house solution, we decided to experiment with external services, and decided on trying out the well-known ChatGPT model provided by OpenAI. We chose the gpt-4 model, as we found the older models were not smart enough for what we were trying to achieve.

Comparing our own model with OpenAI's, there was no big difference. The *Llama 3* model sometimes likes to be more "creative" in their answers, making up information that it was not provided, which is a usual symptom in AI chat models called hallucination. ChatGPT seems to be less prone to this, with the newer models possibly eliminating this issue in our case. Since guaranteeing that our own model is up and running and reachable at any time is harder than relying on an external service, we decided to keep both options in, which we can toggle on our end.

Both solutions virtually work the same, where we provide a pre-defined instruction, along with the character description, and send the conversation along with it, to let the AI answer the questions asked. Both the instructions and an example for the description can be seen on the next page.

You are role-playing as a character with a specific background, personality, and set of objectives. Your responses should be consistent with the given personality and goals. If asked about if you are a social entrepreneur, politely decline to answer. Provide rather concise and brief responses. You mustn't share your whole background at once, in one answer. Specific details of your background should only be shared if they are directly asked about. Avoid wide and general explanations about your knowledge, answer as briefly as possible, even for general questions. If asked about your friends or people you know, only mention one of them.

Figure P2M1.36 The instruction given to the conversational AI

You are Lukas, the founder of Toast Ale, a company dedicated to turning surplus bread into high-quality craft beer. Your mission is twofold: to combat food waste by repurposing bread that would otherwise be

discarded and to raise awareness about the environmental impact of food waste. By brewing beer from surplus bread, you not only create a delicious product but also support charities focused on building a sustainable food system. Every pint of Toast Ale sold contributes to this cause, helping to address food waste and support initiatives that promote environmental stewardship. Through your work, you inspire others to rethink their approach to waste and take meaningful action to protect the planet. You know Tom, the founder of some kind of shoe company, John, the founder of some homeless aid program, and Alex, a cool guy interested in the environment.

Figure P2M1.37 An example personality description for one of the social entrepreneurs.

P2M1 3.1.3 Speech-to-Text AI

Finally, when the conversational AI has given us an answer to the player's question, we must "read it aloud" in a voice suited to the character the player is currently speaking to. Since we have multiple different characters, we had to choose a solution which would provide multiple different voices for our NPCs.

We decided to use the services provided by a company called LMNT, as they develop a solution suited specifically for game development. We could quickly integrate their technology into our game, and we found the services they provide to be perfect for our goals. Even for free, they provide multiple character voices to choose from, enabling us to create a diverse set of characters just as we wanted.

Unfortunately, it did not support Italian which was necessary for the pilot. Therefore, we moved to the Amazon Polly service that supports more languages. Integration was also straightforward and well supported.

P2M1 3.1.4 General game flow and feel

When the first player starts the game, they are greeted by a simple starting room, which allows them to get their bearings in the virtual world. This room can be seen below.

Figure P2M1.38 Game start screen

On the **left**, you can see the **Settings Panel**, where you can customize the global game settings. These include the number of conversations with characters per round, the time allowed for each conversation, and a new feature: the game can now be played without a time limit. By default, there is **no time limit**, so if you want to play with one, please enable it at the bottom (this will turn off the no-timer option). [Note that this feature was added as part of the post-evaluation adaptation, and is different from the stricter flow enforced in the pilots.]

On the **right**, you can see the player **Selection Panel**. The next player can now be **chosen dynamically**. The panel shows the player's name, which was set in the lobby. This panel will also appear later in the game, after the set number of conversations with characters has been completed. At that point, players will spawn in another room, where the next player can also be selected. [Note that this feature was added as part of the post-evaluation adaptation, and is different from the stricter flow enforced in the pilots.]

Only when the player clicks on the "Start Game" button will the game actually begin, by relocating them to the previously discussed Mockup Room, where the players can choose the character, they wish to speak to, by selecting an available pinpoint on the city miniature, as seen below.

Figure P2M1.39 Characters spoken to indicated

The above image shows five characters, which have already been spoken to, in white. These NPCs can be revisited and asked further questions if desired. The red marker, however, shows a character not been spoken to yet. When the player points their controller at their chosen marker and pulls the trigger button, they will be transported to the corresponding character in the city.

Originally we placed the player high above the city to allow them to select the character they wish to speak to, but according to feedback it was both nauseating and confusing, due to the combination of a sudden perspective shift and having to look physically downwards, not to mention the fear someone could experience from being so high up above the city skyline. This new mockup room, while easing the player's dizziness, also allows them to select their new destination easier, as they don't have to turn around physically to see each of the markers. The old bird's eye perspective view can be seen below, with older icons for the pinpoints as well. These older icons were also changed to the new pinpoint icons, which are more commonly used, so the players should be more familiar with them.

Figure P2M1.40 Old bird's-eye-view perspective

Once the player selects a character they wish to talk to, they will be transported to the city, in front of the selected citizen, as seen below:

Figure P2M1.41 Character conversation view

There, the player is given a microphone, which only serves visual and communicational purposes (they don't have to *physically* speak into it). If the player presses the trigger button again and holds it down, the microphone will start recording, which is shown by it turning red. When the player wants to finish talking and subsequently let the character they are talking to answer, they simply have to release the held button. After a short while, the character will answer. While they are speaking, the microphone will turn grey, to signal to the player that they are incapable of recording at the moment. Once the character has finished

their dialogue, the microphone will turn blue to indicate that the player can start recording again. See the pictures below for comparison:

Figure P2M1.42 Conversation status indicators

In the beginning of the game, only one of the above pinpoints is shown. During conversations with the characters, if they mention another NPC (or their company), their marker is revealed, which is accompanied by a notification which pops up in front of the player. Each character has a list of other characters which they know, and if asked may talk about them, but they do not know their whole descriptions, only a few words, like “someone who owns a bike sharing company”, just enough to get the players interested. If the player fails to ask a question which would reveal a new marker, at the end of the conversation, the NPC is “forced” to mention a character which has not been revealed yet (if any exist). This forced mentioning is to keep the game moving and fresh, after all, the players have no way to know about them. The notification which pops up when a new character is mentioned can be seen in Figure P2M1.43.

Figure P2M1.43 Message indicating a new character was discovered

Originally the plan was to let the player talk freely like in a real conversation, without having to record their questions manually. We found out during testing, that the players would approach the game as a real-life conversation, always cutting into the answers given by the characters. This would initiate another “question” towards the AI, and since there is always a small delay before the answer comes, would have to be handled some way: either the characters ignore the players while they themselves are speaking, or they “cancel” their dialogue and start a new one if the player says something. The latter option confused our players even more, while the first one did not provide enough feedback to the players about whether the AI could “hear” them, so we decided to make the conversations more tactile by giving the players a microphone, on which we could show the state of the conversation (listening, talking etc.) in a more intuitive way. This enables communication towards the player in which they are *presumably* more familiar than traditional “gaming” methods: making the microphone red while recording is a common symbol used in many places, along with having to hold the button down like an old school voice recorder.

In the pilots, the players had limited time for their conversations, to make the whole game session fit reasonably within a physical lesson. This is shown by a hovering text above the character’s head, indicating how much time they have. If the timer expires, the NPC will finish their dialogue without allowing the player to ask any further questions, then the player will be returned to the appropriate room. The timer can be seen below, first when counting down, and then when the conversation ended. After the pilots, timers were made optional, and a button to leave the conversation was added. Figure P2M1.44 and Figure P2M1.45 show the timer as it appeared in the pilots.

Figure P2M1.44 Conversation timer

Figure P2M1.45 Conversation timer expired

Initially we tried to limit conversations by the number of questions instead of time. This made sense from a developer standpoint, as for each question we generate an appropriate response with our AI pipeline, but found out that the players would “waste” their opportunities by saying hello, asking for the character’s name etc., which would make sense in a real-world conversation, but ultimately serve no real purpose in the game. These questions, however, allow the players to become more immersed in the virtual world, as it imitates getting to know a real person, hence we decided to switch to a time-based limit instead.

Each player has a set number of times they can choose a character to speak with, after which they must hand over the virtual reality headset to the next person. This is achieved by having “break rooms” which the player will be transported to after a conversation, instead of the mockup room. There are two variants: one when only a single player’s turn has passed, and one when *every* player has gotten their turn already, and a new round has started, with the first player receiving the headset. These two variants can be seen below, they function identically to the starting room, the difference being the text which indicates what the player is supposed to do.

Figure P2M1.46 End of turn and end of round popups

The game itself has no definite end state; the players can keep returning to each of the characters to learn more. Since time in a lesson is limited, the end of round break room can be used as an end state, to signal that everyone got their turn in the game a few times, but the players can go back into the virtual world if they wish to do so.

We also found out during testing, that when the characters took long to answer without any visual feedback, the players would get impatient or confused, hence we decided to add a “thinking bubble” to visualize the character thinking about their answer, which can be seen in Figure P2M1.47. With cloud-based voice-to-text and text-to-voice solutions the waiting times are typically very short, but in case of a delay a more familiar animation with dots in a circle is displayed. [Note that the later enhancement was part of the post-evaluation adaptation.]

Figure P2M1.47 Thinking bubbles

P2M1 3.2 Making a living world

To make the city seem more lived-in and immersive, we decided to add details, that together would add up to make the experience as we envisioned it. These are detailed below.

P2M1 3.2.1 Randomized Citizens

Our first choice was to add citizens that would roam the streets, so our characters would not be alone and stand out in the empty cities. Since we already could “dress up” our NPCs like we wanted, the next step was to add a method to randomize these citizens and also make them walk along the sidewalks. The generated models can be seen below.

Figure P2M1.48 Procedurally generated models

Since these citizens would only serve as background characters, we decided that we shouldn’t put too much effort into their simulation, so we agreed on having them walk between designated waypoints. This can be seen in the picture below, where the white spheres represent these waypoints. In the final version, the spheres would be hidden, and the characters would walk between designated light posts.

Figure P2M1.49 Sidewalk simulation with waypoints

Below, the final results can be seen, albeit not with the final buildings which would be used to furnish the city (to be discussed in a later chapter).

Figure P2M1.50 Citizens walk around the whole city, using lamps as waypoints

P2M1 3.2.2 Vehicles around the city

Cars can also be found everywhere in the town. These are currently also simple design elements aiming for the players to experience the environment as more realistic.

Figure P2M1.51 Traffic in the city

P2M1 3.2.3 Procedural Building Generation

To speed up development time, an internal tool for generating models of buildings in different styles was created. This allowed us to be far more productive than modelling by hand, while also ensuring that we could keep the diversity of the virtual city high, as it would be in a real town.

Buildings are made up of predefined, smaller segments. These segments are modeled by hand and are assembled to form the facade of the various buildings. Below, some of these segments can be seen, in different architectural styles, ranging from an “eastern bloc” style to a more developed, richer style.

Figure P2M1.52 Different textures & models for the segments

The algorithm generates the models on a given plot of any polygonal shape, with a variable parameter set. (number of stories, materials to use, roof slope and height etc.)

It first calculates reference points the different segments should be placed onto, as seen below:

Figure P2M1.53 *Calculating the reference points for the segment assembly*

Then the segments themselves are copied to these points accordingly:

Figure P2M1.54 *Segments separated by type*

Figure P2M1.55 Assembled building (as seen in modelling software)

The final result can be seen above. Using this tool, we were able to speed up the development process of the game, by ensuring a sufficient level of uniqueness among the buildings the city consists of, without the need for hand modelling any of them.

Figure P2M1.56 Stylized shading used in final project

To make the world diverse, we also added multiple styles of buildings, which together would emulate different districts: poorer and richer ones. These styles also included details, such as the “poorer” districts having graffiti. These can be seen below.

Figure P2M1.57 Facades

P2M1 3.2.4 NPC environments

In post-evaluation adaptation, a unique animated model and a background environment was created for each of the sixteen characters. Both the character models and the objects in the environment offer clues and conversation topics for the exploration of the NPC's activities. See fig0 to fig1 for all models.

Figure P2M1.58 Individual character environments

Figure P2M1.59 Tim sells shoes with social mission.

Figure P2M1.60 Amy leads a bank lending to micro-entrepreneurs.

Figure P2M1.61 Sebastian operates e-bikes.

Figure P2M1.62 Lukas's brewery uses leftover bread.

Figure P2M1.63

John organizes volunteers to build houses for people in need.

Figure P2M1.64 Lisa works in energy sharing.

Figure P2M1.65

Mira offers services supporting sustainable farming.

Figure P2M1.66 Ingrid is a social worker who helps disadvantaged youth.

Figure P2M1.67

Sophia sells health insurance.

Figure P2M1.68 Livia is an investment broker.

Figure P2M1.69 Jamie works as a car mechanic.

Figure P2M1.70

Alex works as a firefighter and a fire safety expert.

Figure P2M1.71 Martin is a farmer.

Figure P2M1.72 Amelie is a disadvantaged youth with addiction issues.

Figure P2M1.73 Nina operates a high-risk sports betting scheme from her bar.

Figure P2M1.74 Marcus gives high-cost loans to people in need.

P2M1 3.3 Collecting data

Measurement data is collected with two techniques. One is the Emotibit device, which is able to stream multiple data streams from the body. With this device, we can measure different body signs, like heart rate, body temperature, nervous system responses, etc.

The other technique is eye-tracking. Although the HP Reverb G2 Omnicept has eye-tracking capabilities, it was not usable in our game. We had to implement our own version using raycasting, which is not as accurate as the built-in tracker could be, since it doesn't literally follow the eyes' movement but simply casts rays in the central direction of the headset and finds objects intersecting with this ray, so in other words, objects that are in the middle of our picture will be found. However, this is still very useful for our measurement purposes since, in the dominant ratio of the time, players look in the middle area of the frame they see, so mistakes of our own implementation are negligible compared to the successful identification of objects. Eye-tracking is used to log the objects the player was looking at, and also the duration of these moments. With this information, we can draw conclusions about what elements captured the player's attention more.

P2M1 4 User Manual with demonstration

P2M1 4.1 Preparations

Since our game is made for VR, **having a VR headset is essential** to play. Specifically, the program was written for the **HP Reverb G2 Omnicept** device. Theoretically, the game should work with any VR headset running on **Windows Mixed Reality**, however, other devices were not tested during the development phase and the logging of useful information for the management team would probably fail since it is designed for the sensor capabilities of the G2 Omnicept. Because of this dependency and the usage of other Windows-based services like the speech component, this game is exclusively **made for Windows operating system**. Figure P2M1.75 shows the suggested device, the HP Reverb G2 Omnicept.

Figure P2M1.75 HP Reverb G2 Omnicept

P2M1 4.2 Start of the game

After starting the program and putting the headset on, you find yourself in a starting room. There's a floating textbox with a **START button**. You should use your controller to point on the button, and press the **trigger button** on your controller. Figure P2M1.76 shows the trigger button, which can be found on the front of the controller. The game handles every click interaction with this button. Figure P2M1.77 shows the starting room.

Figure P2M1.76 The trigger button

Figure P2M1.77 The starting room

P2M1 4.3 Main scenes

The game flow consists of two main scenes, on one, the player sees the mockup and is able to select a destination to travel to, while on the other, the player is in the city having a conversation with an NPC.

P2M1 4.3.1 Conversation selection scene

The player is located in a room with a mockup in the center. Here you can select destinations by pointing at **location indicator pins** (the ray changes color to blue) and pressing the **trigger button**. Each destination has a character you can talk to. White ones are destinations already visited, while the red pins mark new people to have a conversation with. After clicking on a pin, the player gets teleported to the wanted location, which is of the other main type of scenes. Figure P2M1.78 shows the conversation selection scene.

Figure P2M1.78 Conversation selection scene

P2M1 4.3.2 Conversation scene

The player is in one of the areas of the city where chatting NPCs are located. After teleportation, the conversation is automatically initialized, meaning once the player is there, they can start chatting right away. The conversation is totally voice-driven so the player doesn't have to use keyboard or controllers during a session, which would be uncomfortable in the VR environment.

The character is powered by a Large Language Model, meaning they are **AI chatbots instructed to play a role**. Note that

- Some characters have negative traits or may even be criminals. It is your task to be critical about them and evaluate their activities.
- AI systems can make mistakes, exhibit inherent bias, or hallucinate details they were never instructed about. These are less likely to happen if you keep your conversations on point.

In this activity, players should work in a group of four students. They take turns putting the headset on and talking to the characters, while the others may observe and take notes. Their task is to explore the city and **identify** which characters can be considered **entrepreneurs**, and which are **social entrepreneurs**. The characters in the game have knowledge about and relationships to other characters. The player can reach more of them if they are mentioned in the conversation, so they should ask characters not only

about what they do, but also about their relations to others. Some characters may paint their own activity in a different light than others would, so it could be beneficial to get multiple opinions.

The conversation is always an exchange of messages. The parties cannot interrupt each other. In order to indicate that the student is speaking, they need to hold the grab button on the controller. The color of the virtual microphone changes to blue. Once the button is released, the spoken message is interpreted by the system, and a response is formulated. This may take some seconds and is indicated by thought bubbles appearing above the character as shown in Figure P2M1.47.

The conversations are timed, but students can leave the conversation earlier by pressing the trigger button. they can re-visit characters you have already talked to, but, as there are 16 characters and limited time, the conversations should not be longer than 2-3 minutes.

The students have 40 minutes as a group. One student should talk to two characters, then give the headset to the next student. While the switch is happening, and any time during the activity, they should discuss if the character fits in any of the below categories, based on the traits listed:

Enterprise

- must earn income to survive
- the main goal is making profit
- creates something new
- needs inspiration, creativity, direct action, courage, and fortitude
- meets customer needs
- takes a risk
- may create a new market equilibrium

Social enterprise

- income from trading goods or services
- mission focused
- altruistic
- profits invested into mission
- ownership tied to mission
- new idea solves a social problem (has social impact)
- seeks systemic change

Social services

- governmental agencies
- assist disadvantaged groups

Non-profits

- public funding or donations
- fundraising is a main activity
- works for a social good

Their goal is to correctly identify the entrepreneurs and social entrepreneurs, and find as many social entrepreneurs in the city as possible.

Some characters are based on real-life enterprises exemplifying social enterprises. The names of these businesses were not used to avoid associating them with simplifications or AI hallucinations. However, at

the end of the activity, students receive a brief summary on the real-life inspirations of the social enterprises they have discovered.

Once the conversation has ended, the player is teleported back to the mockup scene, where new pins can be seen. Figure P2M1.79 shows a sketch of the two types of scenes located in the game. The conversation selection scene equals the mockup room, which is a single area. Conversely, a conversation scene can be one of multiple separate areas in the city, namely, one of the locations where AI-buffed NPCs can be found.

Figure P2M1.79 Conversation selection and conversation scenes

P2M1 4.4 Game session

A game session consists of the three types of scenarios: the starting room, the mockup room, and a conversation scene, which can be one of multiple places. The starting room is only present at the beginning. After we have advanced from there, the other two types of scenarios take turns. From the mockup room, we always teleport to a conversation scenario, and from there, we always teleport back to the mockup room.

There is no game ending mechanic, the players can play for as long as they want to, then they have to terminate the game. Generally, the supervising teacher may decide when the session should be finished. In the pilots, they must adhere to the time limits set by the study protocol.

Figure P2M1.80 State machine of the scenarios

P2M2. Heroes: Urban Management for Social Outcomes

P2M2 1 Virtual city

Heroes is a module about urban management. It teaches about the interaction of social and urban subsystems, and the impact of decisions on business and society, in a practical manner. For that purpose, the workings of a virtual city are simulated. While a realistic, working city is most suited for first-person VR exploration, this project requires a bit more abstract overview of the city, so that the functions and the actions of the citizens are all observable.

The players in the game must cooperate to place buildings. These buildings all represent policy decisions and cater to the needs of citizens. Citizens (NPCs) are simulated by tracking their statistics: money, health, nutrition, fatigue, and happiness. We refer to these as NPC *stats*.

P2M2 2 General Description of Buildings and Their Functionality

Buildings in the city affect NPCs. When they need something, they walk or commute to an appropriate building, enter it, and obtain some change to their status inside the building.

Buildings represent subsystems in the city's economy, such as industry, entertainment, healthcare, housing, food supply, and travel. Accordingly, the following buildings can be placed: home, hospital, grocery store, cinema, factory, and parking lot.

The home building is responsible for the NPCs' rest. It slightly increases certain stats. NPCs come here when they are tired and need to rest. This building also plays another significant role: when the player builds such a structure, some NPCs move into the city, thus expanding the city's population.

The hospital is responsible for healing NPCs. It significantly increases certain stats. NPCs go there when they are sick.

The grocery store serves to meet their hunger and daily needs.

The cinema is for NPCs' entertainment. If they have enough money, they come here to enjoy themselves.

The factory is responsible for their livelihood. NPCs earn money here to meet their needs. Another important role of the factory is that the player also receives money from it, in the form of a kind of tax, which can later be used to build new buildings.

Buildings are characterized by the specific status changes they trigger, to what extent, how often these changes would occur, and how many residents could occupy a building at once. The effects are slightly

randomized to make the behavior of NPCs more representative of the overall state, instead of clustering them together.

P2M2 3 General Description of NPC Logic

NPC decisions are based on the NPCs stats. Based on their needs, NPCs determine which type of building to head toward and then plan the route. The pathfinding algorithm checks all currently available buildings that the NPC needs and plans the route to the closest one.

NPC decision making follows a general pattern: every NPC would try to satisfy its most urgent need. The challenge to students playing the game is, in part, to anticipate the needs of the citizens, and provide balanced facilities for them.

P2M2 4 Motion and VR sickness

After co-design and trial sessions, it was concluded that continuous turns in VR should not be used. They confuse the human brain, especially when you can freely move your head but with the controller you initiate a turn. Therefore, the game uses discrete turns with fixed angles. The turn happens almost instantly, but slow enough to allow the player to relate the pre-turn and post-turn positions. Fading/darkening the view during the turn further helps to avoid discomfort.

For navigation, free flying provided a satisfactory experience for most people, and it is easy to use, but there was some negative feedback about it. 3 people out of 20 experienced motion sickness. One of them had prior problems with VR applications even when the person does not have to move around much. The game allows for the use of the tunneling vignette technique, which narrows down the vision of the player during movement. This may make the VR experience less immersive for many people but reduces discomfort for sensitive individuals. Sitting in a chair also reduces vertigo induced by virtual flight.

If a player feels sick, they should stop playing the game with VR headset. The games are playable with keyboard and mouse, so if a player cannot play the game in VR, they can still continue being part of the team and play with them.

In the final version of the module, the players are not flying freely, but they are still hovering above the city. The player has complete control over their horizontal movement with the left joystick, but vertical movement is not affected by this control. As motion sickness was mainly introduced by “diving”, i.e. flying downwards, this eliminates much of the discomfort. Instead, a discrete “change of elevation” can be initiated by a push on the other joystick. This is similar to the discrete rotation, with the same fading technique. One could think of this as changing levels. Pressing the joystick forwards transports us to a level that is a little higher while backwards means a lower level.

The right joystick has another important feature: It is responsible for the player’s turning function. Evidently, if the player presses the joystick to the side, they turn right or left for a fixed angle, with the process being covered by the fade effect.

P2M2 5 Collecting sensor data

P2M2 5.1 HP Virtual reality headset

The users will be wearing the HP Reverb G2 Omnicept Edition virtual reality headset during gameplay. This device is equipped with several sensors capable of measuring certain physiological data from the player. The device can measure the following physiological data:

- Heart rate
- Eye movement
- Cognitive load
- Heart rate variability

In addition, the device is capable of recording acceleration and rotation along the X, Y, and Z axes, as well as capturing images from the cameras on the device. Each piece of data measured by the sensors is tagged with a system, hardware, and Omnicept timestamp. This is important because the different sensors have varying update frequencies, making the timestamp crucial when analyzing data measured at a specific moment.

With the data from the Eye-tracking sensor, it is possible to detect which in-game object the player was looking at in each moment thus creating even more data that can be analyzed later.

P2M2 5.2 Capturing sensor data in the Unity project

To be able to capture the sensor data in a Unity project, the Omnicept SDK needs to be installed first. The Unity package called `Glia.unitypackage`, included in the SDK, must be imported into the project.

There are two possible approaches to querying data. One is subscribing to the sensors, reacting to each new data entry. The other is polling the data at regular intervals. It's important to note that these two approaches can be combined, and it's not necessary to sample all sensors in the same way.

P2M2 5.3 Subscribing to the sensors

The main advantage of this method is that data is only recorded when fresh data is available, which reduces storage requirements. However, the downside is that the timestamps of the entries will differ, which may complicate data analysis. An alternative solution could be to subscribe to all sensors but only record data when fresh data is available from every sensor. In this case, the sensor with the lowest update frequency will be the bottleneck.

P2M2 5.4 Polling sensor data

This method can be useful if we want to take a snapshot of sensor data in response to a specific event in the game. In this case, the data are stored in instance variables, which we can record simultaneously, thus allowing us to obtain information from all sensors at that particular moment. Although this method can facilitate the analysis of information, the storage may not be optimally utilized because there are sensors with update frequencies that are orders of magnitude slower than others, and data from such sensors might be recorded multiple times.

In the project we decided to go with the first solution since it was important to record all the data, while also considering the need to use storage space efficiently during data recording. Storage space efficiency would be crucial if we wanted to store the data in an online storage.

The players will also be wearing the EmotiBit device. EmotiBit is a wearable sensor module for capturing high-quality emotional, physiological, and movement data. All the data from both devices will be captured while playing the game, so it can be analyzed later.

P2M2 6 User manual

During the game, you float over the city, and you see the other students as floating capsules. You can see the rays coming from their controllers, and see where they are pointing and what they are doing.

You can **turn your head** to look around. You can use the **right-hand** controller **joystick to turn** left or right without physically turning your head, in small jumps. You can move the same **joystick up or down to rise up or sink lower**, also in small jumps.

In order to move around, you can **drag** yourself over the ground. For this, you need to hold down the button on **the bottom of the controller**, and **pull** the controller towards yourself. You can use any or both of the two controllers.

At the beginning of the game, a minimal city with a few plots for buildings is shown, as illustrated by Figure P2M2.81.

Figure P2M2.81 *Game start*

You can point and on the big concrete squares (the plots) and use the **trigger button**. The building selection menu is displayed (Figure P2M2.82) as long as you hold the button. You must point at the appropriate building, and just release the button to finalize your choice.

Figure P2M2.82 Building selection menu

After selecting the building, a “hologram” version of it appears (Figure P2M2.83). Another player has to point on the hologram and perform the same building gesture to finish the building. When residential buildings are built, citizens appear in the city. Their most pressing need is indicated above them with an icon. The building and citizens are shown in Figure P2M2.84.

Figure P2M2.83 Building suggestion

Figure P2M2.84 Building ready

Once you build facilities that address their needs, citizens would walk there (Figure P2M2.85).

Figure P2M2.85 Factory with workers approaching

The statistics of citizens and associated building as follows:

- stamina** – they rest in the **Residential buildings**
- money** – they earn income working in **Factories**
- nutrition** – they visit a **Restaurant**
- health** – they must go to a **Hospital**
- happiness** – they can visit the **Cinema**

The buildings are shown In Figure P2M2.86.

Figure P2M2.86 Citizens with their driving needs indicated

If any statistic of a citizen drops to zero, they consider the city unlivable, and move out, disappearing from the game. Your goal, as a group working together, is to avoid that, while you grow the city as large as possible.

The icon over the citizen's head always shows its most pressing need, and it moves towards the nearest available building catering for that need. If it appears that the citizen will not be able to reach the building in time, the icon blinks in red. This indicates a shortcoming in the city setup that needs to be remedied.

You can open the statistics overview (Figure P2M2.87) to see overall data about the citizens by pressing the top button on your left-hand controller. The colorful pictograms show the average value of each statistic, while the red ones on the right show the lowest value that belongs to any one citizen.

Figure P2M2.87 Welfare statistics popup

After successfully keeping the happiness of the characters above a threshold by paying attention to their needs, the city will expand, as shown in Figure P2M2.88. As the city expands, the citizens must travel greater distances if some facilities are not available close by. This can cause them to leave the city if they must do it on foot. **Parking lots** connect parts of the city by letting citizens use cars between them. It is recommended to utilize them when expanding the city.

Figure P2M2.88 City expansion

The players then have a race against time, to expand the town to the largest size they can before the timer runs out. However, it is not as easy as it sounds, as they need to strategically spend their money on buildings, while also placing those buildings in the appropriate place. Finding ways to cooperate and act fast is necessary for managing a successful city.

P2M3. Painters – Business planning

P2M3 1 Introduction

Painters is a module where the knowledge about social entrepreneurship is materialized on a *business model canvas* (BMC) exercise. The module objective is testing a new class method based on decentralized participation of students employing co-creation tools in a virtual classroom.

The activity has been designed for the participation of four students and a moderator who also acts as the experimental session controller.

The room is created thanks to the integration of Moodle and AWS virtual machines carried out for the project platform infrastructure. [Note that in the post-evaluation adaptation phase, e-DIPLOMA partner Brainstorm has launched its **Edison OnCloud** service (<https://www.brainstorm3d.com/edison-oncloud-a-new-tool-to-transform-presentations-with-cloud-based-innovation/>). This offers a dominant alternative to the EC2 virtual machine solution used in the e-DIPLOMA pilots and described in this document. Adaptors are advised to inquire with Brainstorm which solution is more conducive to their needs.]

The students connect to the virtual machine through the available course in the e-Diploma Platform after previous authentication.

The access is allowed after the execution of the installer provided and downloaded from the same Moodle platform. The access to the virtual machine is achieved thanks to NICE DCV tool client software, seamlessly integrated. After the client execution, triggered by the Moodle webpage a window opens and the windows machine desktop is presented.

The VM is running Brainstorm Edison Software where the BMC project is running. The students are invited by the moderator to carry out the completion of the BMC areas in turns during a determined time duration.

The students are allowed and motivated to communicate within the group to discuss the items to add to every canvas area. The communication between the students is allowed by MS Teams conferencing tool. Within the conferencing tool the students can query and consult four AI Personas developed for the prototype. The personas' knowledge is focused on social entrepreneurship and the students will be supported on this topic while they are completing the BMC exercise. The training sessions about the business canvas exercise will be conducted in the considered partners facilities, the activity flow and setup is reported below in the following section.

P2M3 2 Activity flow

P2M3 2.1 Setup

Every training session participant as student will need the following equipment:

- personal computer connected to internet
- installed e-Diploma EC2 Edison access App (automatically downloaded and installed by the e-Diploma project platform)
- installed MS Teams App [During the pilots, pre-created user accounts were used for the purposes of data protection and anonymity. Later, however, every user is required to register herself through regular means, be that individual or through an education provider.]
- WI-FI access point to support Emotibit connection [only required in the pilots, or for later studies]
- Emotibit Sensor with external battery [only required in the pilots, or for later studies]

The mentioned equipment is supposed to be installed in separate rooms to emulate the remote condition. In case this would not be possible, the participants should wear headsets provided with microphones in order to avoid echo generation in the teleconferencing system.

P2M3 2.2 Moderator Manual

The moderator of the session is in charge of several tasks and it is vital for the experimental session results generation, collection and reliability.

The tasks to be completed are the following ones:

- Start MS Teams session
- Verify that the students are instrumented with the *Emotibit* sensor.
- Set up the *Edison* Virtual room for the exercise activity.
- *Moderate the session.*
- *Extract* the *experimental data* generated from the several devices.
- *Save the data* to the proper cloud storage.

The tasks listed will be described in detail in the next sections.

The first input that should be monitored by the moderator is the *sessionID*, data that will identify the session within all the experimental data generators involved.

The generators modules are the following:

- Emotibit logger
- Teams transcriptor
- Business model canvas (BMC)
- Excel sheet

To save all the data files generated the *sessionID* should be employed for the files naming, as far as the *subjectID*, in case it is needed.

These details are included in the following sections.

P2M3 2.2.1 MS Teams

The video conferencing tool selected for the BMC exercise acts in several ways. The first and main feature is to communicate with the students and moderator. This last actor will activate the session recording and posteriorly collect the session transcription as one of the experimental session results.

The session recording will be triggered just when the BMC exercise starts, avoiding recording the previous phases of systems and devices verification and setup.

To start the session recording: select More actions → Record and transcribe → Start recording.

P2M3 2.2.2 Emotibit

The painters prototype involves the participation of four students concurrently. The assessment of the activity of these subjects includes the collection of physiological signals captured employing the Emotibit Sensors.

The moderator should verify the presence of the Emotibit (moderator can be acting remotely) and the software that is in charge of collecting the signals (Figure P2M3.89) is properly configured with the proper subjects and session identifiers.

The Emotibit software employed for painters is the executable called:

eDiplomaLineaBase.exe

If all the steps to set up the Emotibit have been properly done, the mentioned software will collect the signals and store them in a log file in the subject local machine.

Figure P2M3.89 Emotibit software

The operator will name the LOG File (User id in the figure above) by inserting the sessionID and subjectID. In this way the file will be identified properly for the posterior data collection and storage.

P2M3 2.2.3 Edison Software

The following step for the moderator is to set up the session in the project platform infrastructure. the moderator should access the course through the Moodle platform (Figure P2M3.90).

The following link provides direct access to the room creation.

<https://cg.iit.bme.hu:3004/>

Figure P2M3.90 Courses in Moodle

Press the link Prototype 2 – Social Entrepreneurship

Figure P2M3.91 Moodle login

After login (Figure P2M3.91) the course page (Figure P2M3.92) appears, click **Painters**

Figure P2M3.92 Course page

The lobby page (Figure P2M3.93) will appear.

Figure P2M3.93 Lobby page

If it is the first time that the VM is accessed, the installation of the NICE DCV installer is needed (brown box). After the installation the participants should be added to the room. Press the big blue +1 button, then drag the user inside the room (Figure P2M3.94).

Figure P2M3.94 Room in the lobby

After the user addition, click on the yellow lock button, to close it. After this step the NICE DCV client will be ready and the user will be able to run it by pressing the play button. (Figure P2M3.95)

Figure P2M3.95 Launching a session

After this step the play button will substitute the box button on the right. Press the cloud button at the left side of the screen. After pressing it, a counter that visualizes the time needed to instantiate the VM will run.

Figure P2M3.96 Starting up cloud instance

When the instantiation time finishes (Figure P2M3.96), the play button on the right side should be pressed (Figure P2M3.97) and the NICE DCV client runs. Confirm the credentials presented on the client and access the VM desktop.

Figure P2M3.97 Joining the session

At this point the first step is to run Microsoft Teams App:

The moderator will:

1. If the moderator is not physically with the students, they should run MS Teams on the local machine employed. This is needed for communication with the students.
2. Start the Teams App on the virtual machine, with the same user, selecting the add device option. It is really important that VM's Teams is added in this way. The Teams app on the virtual machine is needed to insert the video feed of the participants inside Edison. MS Teams should be already configured with NDI production capabilities.
3. Run Edison SW selecting the e-Diploma Painters project (Painters 2), employing the direct access on the VM desktop (Figure P2M3.98).

Figure P2M3.98 Edison BMC project shortcut in Windows desktop of the Virtual machine

Once the project starts, the main view of the virtual room is presented, and should be modified to remove some areas that are not helpful for the exercise (Figure P2M3.99, red shaded area).

Figure P2M3.99 Start view of BMC Edison Project

To do this the moderator should press the buttons in the tools bar presented above in the SW interface (Figure P2M3.100).

Figure P2M3.100 Edison toolbar

After this operation, the result should be similar to the following figure (Figure P2M3.101).

Figure P2M3.101 BMC exercise adjusted view

The last step is enable the Form area where the students will interact with the BMC slide. To do this the user should activate the form area in the previously introduced View Areas Control, shown in Figure P2M3.102.

Figure P2M3.102 View areas control

Activating this button will reveal the **Form** Area, where all the control of the BMC slide are placed. The **Form** area is visualized below in Figure P2M3.103 (red shaded area).

Figure P2M3.103 BMC exercise with form visualization

Set up the video input coming from Teams inside Edison. The configuration panel (Figure P2M3.105) should be opened pressing the wrench icon on the upper tools palette (Figure P2M3.104).

Figure P2M3.104 Wrench icon in the tools palette

Figure P2M3.105 Configuration panel

The students' Windows inside Edison's virtual Room will be configured for every participant, the moderator is the first and corresponds to the central image placed at the bottom of the virtual room view, the following 2 actors are related to the windows presented on the left side of the virtual room, the 4th and 5th on the right side.

- The moderator will now press the slide ("Business Canvas") on the list presented at the top of the upper part at left of the viewport (red shaded rectangle in Figure P2M3.106). This action triggers the BMC slide visualization in the viewport.

Figure P2M3.106 BMC working area and interface

5. The last steps to prepare the project for the exercise session are:
 - (1) configure the questions that will be visualized in every area of the BMC
 - (2) configure the timer accordingly to the use the moderator decides.

1. The questions can be configured in the **config** tab that can be consulted in the red shaded area of Figure P2M3.105. The content of the tab is presented in Figure P2M3.107.

Figure P2M3.107 Content tab

These questions are the main support to the students that will carry out the activity. To visualize the questions during the exercise a specific button is presented in each of the areas where the students will work. The key Partners Area example is shown below in Figure P2M3.108.

Figure P2M3.108 Support questions in BMC exercise

2. The timer to control the tasks execution can be configured in **countdown** tab at the side of the **config** one already mentioned (red shaded area, Figure P2M3.109). The timer can be adjusted to the required value and started or stopped in case of necessity.

Figure P2M3.109 Countdown tab

At this point the setup is ready and the students can access the room following the same steps presented at the beginning of this section. These steps will be explained again in the student's Manual.

P2M3 2.2.4 Moderate Session

The experimental session can now start. The students access the VM employing NICE DCV clients. Moderator verifies they are able to control and move things by questions through the Teams conferencing tool.

First of all the Moderator should confirm with the students that the computers that they are employing have the **same time and date**. This is vital for the posterior results processing where the traceability per time of the collected data should be consistent especially in this case where multiple machines are employed concurrently.

To moderate the session and provide to the students a correct tasks' time management a timer has been added to the Edison slides to constantly visualize the time spent on every area. To also reduce the possibility of time managing errors, an excel file is provided to the moderator to support this activity.

The moderating tool is an excel file where the moderator inserts the session's start time. with this input the excel sheet calculates the timings for the session. The moderator should then monitor the time and ask the current exercise actor to leave the control to the following student. As it is difficult to strictly follow the time schedule (i.e. if the students are collaborating, to interrupt them may corrupt the results) the moderator will note the delay in case a student's turn results longer than expected.

Once the students control verification is done:

- The moderator will save the Edison Project as a new version, naming this version with the ***sessionID*** already defined (see section P2M3 2.2).
- the moderator will start the VM screen recording (via OBS), through EDISON interface, pressing the record button on the tools bar (yellow shaded area in Figure P2M3.110).

Figure P2M3.110 Record button

The same session is also recorded by the Teams App since the call is started. To also include the screen activity in teams recording, would be necessary that the moderator shares the Edison window through the MS Teams call window (Figure P2M3.111).

Figure P2M3.111 Screen sharing in Teams

The moderator will support the exercise completion, verifying that the students complete all the nine regions of the BMC.

The regions sequence selected for this exercise is the following:

1. Customer Segments
2. Value Propositions
3. Channels
4. Customer Relationships
5. Revenue Streams
6. Key Resources
7. Key Activities
8. Key Partners
9. Cost structure

When the session time elapsed, the moderator should dismiss the students and close the session in Teams. Closing the MS Teams session will trigger the end of the recording and session transcription.

At this time the moderator should collect the data generated for the session:

- MS Teams session recording and transcription.
- Emotibits signals recordings (one per each student)

- BMC exercise (from Edison Project or Teams recording).

P2M3 2.3 Student Manual

The Student will go through three steps to complete the exercise:

- Join the MS Teams session
- Access the Moodle Room where the exercise should be completed
- carry out the exercise collaborating with the others students involved

The student will be guided by the moderator, but to ease this task and better exploit the session and exercise, the instructions of the three main steps are reported below.

MS Teams session

The student should join the MS Teams session initiated by the moderator.

Access Edison's Virtual room for the exercise activity.

The following link provides direct access to e-DIPLOMA Moodle (Figure P2M3.112).

<https://cg.iit.bme.hu:3004/>

Figure P2M3.112 Moodle page

Press the link Prototype 2 – Social Entrepreneurship (Figure P2M3.114).

Figure P2M3.113 Login to Moodle

After Login (Figure P2M3.113) the following screen appears, click **Painters**.

Figure P2M3.114 Course page

The lobby page will appear (Figure P2M3.115).

Figure P2M3.115 Lobby page

If it is the first time that the VM is accessed, the installation of the NICE DCV installer is needed (brown box). The teacher will have prepared cloud resources and opened a room in the Lobby. Students can join the open room or leave it. When all students have joined, the teacher locks the room (Figure P2M3.116) and starts the session.

Figure P2M3.116 Locked room

Once the session has been started, the join session button (Figure P2M3.117) should be pressed and the NICE DCV client runs, giving access to the VM desktop.

Figure P2M3.117 Join session

The exercise

To carry out the exercise the student should edit the text field that are provided in the FORM and DATA section of the presented SW interface (Figure below).

Figure P2M3.118 Business Model Canvas Exercise Main view

In the FORM area (Figure P2M3.118, Green shaded area) several buttons are presented and allow zooming on the different BMC areas, pushing on the button related to each of the areas.

Figure P2M3.119 Form Area to control the zoom during the exercise completion

Some areas, due to a doubled size with respect to the others, have double buttons: one to zoom on the upper part and one for the lower part.

In the DATA area (red rectangle in 101, detail in figure) the business model canvas areas can be edited adding up to six tickets on every region. At the start of every control area (Key Partners, figure below) there are two buttons that allow for visualizing the support questions to help to create content on top of these areas.

Figure P2M3.120 Question buttons

The red shaded buttons in Figure P2M3.120 allow to visualize the questions in the working area (Figure P2M3.121)

Figure P2M3.121 Support questions in working area

The Students can fill the text fields provided to create a post-it to place in every area of the business model canvas. The result is shown in Figure P2M3.122.

Figure P2M3.122 Adding notes to the BMC using Edison interface

With these features, the student is able to collaborate and co create during the educational session.

The most relevant detail to support a fluid and entertaining activity is to follow the moderator instructions and edit the areas just when the student has the control turn.

Personas' support and interaction

The students have the opportunity to communicate with artificial intelligence personas trained on the topics of the social entrepreneurship and focused on sustainable energy production and sharing, which is the main focus of the exercise.

There are 5 personas that can be consulted through the teams call interface, employing the chat part (see image Below). To activate the chat of the Teams call, the student should press the "chat" (green shaded area) button in the upper part of the window and then write the message to the persona in the yellow shaded area. The response from the persona will be received in the chat history (red shaded area.) This response will be visible for every student and moderator in the Teams call (Figure P2M3.123). Alternatively, students can also chat individually to the personas by starting a one-on-one chat with them.

Figure P2M3.123 Chatting with the support Personas in the MS Teams Call Window

To contact each of the available personas in the call chat, the student should type the “@” character followed by the name of the persona. For an individual chat, it is enough to write the name (without the “@” character) in the search bar of Teams.

The personas available are the following:

- Molly [e-Diploma]
- Marius [e-Diploma]
- Bob [e-Diploma]
- Ruben [e-Diploma]
- Henry [e-Diploma]

P2M4.Allies – Social Human Resources and Team Management

P2M4 1 Module description

e-DIPLOMA Allies is a singleplayer educational game, where the player must recruit and manage a team as a social entrepreneur. The game is made up of two parts that must be played simultaneously. In one part the player must interview applicants who are roleplayed by a Large Language Model (LLM). In the other part the player must manage the hired team members by assigning them jobs, monitoring their performance and behavior and reacting accordingly. This is done simultaneously while hiring other team members. There is a limited time to do this, and performance of the player is primarily measured based on the final team performance accompanied by the growth, income and impact of the company.

The primary goal is to teach the player how to perform an interview efficiently. This consists of interacting with different personalities, maintaining a healthy conversation and negotiating a wage. The player must also find out how to effectively assess the applicant's abilities, skills and shortcomings. These impact their behavior and performance during the game. Also, the game encourages efficient multitasking as time does not stop during the interview. On the contrary, new tasks and problems can arise dynamically and must be handled swiftly. The player must converse with the applicants in English or Italian, and they will answer in the same language.

P2M4 1.1 Technical background

The game was created in Unity. The backstories of the applicants were partly written by ChatGPT and later revised and rewritten manually. The default LLM that is used is the Llama 3 70B model available from here <https://huggingface.co/casperhansen/llama-3-70b-instruct-awq>. The application also supports other LLM-s available through the OpenAI API like ChatGPT. The applicant images are generated through stable diffusion.

The game is configurable through a JSON file that lists the available applicants. It describes the characters backstory (the prompt sent to the LLM), its traits, skills and values and preferred wage.

P2M4 2 Game rules

The company that the player must lead is a simplified version of an existing social enterprise model. The goal of the company is to sell used goods. They contact people and try to solicit donations. They arrange the transport of the solicited goods then store and organize them in a warehouse. Later these can be bought by other customers in the store.

The player starts with an initial budget that is displayed on the top of the screen. It is measured in \$/hour, that is how much USD is currently available to spend on recruitment. On the left a scrollable list shows the current applicants with illustrated portraits. In the middle a chat window shows the interview history with

each applicant. The player can type messages here and will receive answers from the LLM. Each person has a distinct personality that influences how they react. On the right the current state of the company and its employees is shown.

The top shows the current organization of the company and its prestige. Organization represents the capabilities of its management. Prestige represents its popularity and popular consensus on its ability to fulfill customer demands.

The lower part shows the currently selected applicant. Each applicant has some hidden traits that will be shown here (in blue if positive, or in red if negative). These are initially hidden but can be found by the player when interacting with the applicant. The traits can be the following: *lone wolf, teamworker, organizer, autonomous, follower, lazy, eager, introvert, extrovert, field worker, office worker, driver, non-driver*.

Each applicant has a distinct personality. On one hand this is roleplayed by the AI Chat model, but on the other hand it is described by numerical statistics. Skills mentioned earlier are like this. They describe how well the person is suited to do certain jobs. A different aspect is the applicant's values and personality. An efficient team must have consistent values across its members. Values are organized on 4 categorizes:

- freedom-cooperation
- fun-sobriety
- intelligence-kindness
- excellence-equality

Each applicant is assigned one of these from every category in accordance with their backstory. These are hidden initially but can be discovered during conversations alongside their traits. They appear to the right of the discovered traits. A team with little to no conflicting values will perform much more efficiently than a team with many conflicting values. The conflicts are displayed to the player through messages from the employees where they complain about the others who have conflicting values.

The Hire button is on the bottom that can be used by the player to hire the applicant. An initial wage request is displayed next to it, but it can be negotiated. It changes to a Dismiss button if the person is already hired.

In the middle two columns are displayed. On the left the current team is shown. The player can see here what they are doing currently. With the settings button (cogwheel) they can change which tasks they are allowed to take. Speak bubbles also show up here from time to time, and they indicate a problem in the team that lowers efficiency. On the right the currently available tasks are displayed.

The following jobs are available:

- **Solicit donations:** contact people for donations. Upon completion a Delivery task is generated
- **Deliver goods:** bring the solicited goods to the warehouse. Upon completion a Stock shelves task is generated.
- **Stock shelves:** organize and administrate the goods. Upon completion the number of available goods increases.
- **Sell goods:** sells goods from the warehouse to customers.
- **Promote the store:** increase the prestige of the company generating more Sale tasks.

- **Manage the company:** increase company organization to be more efficient.

The player can select any or none of the following jobs: *Deliver goods*, *Stock shelves*, *Sell goods*. If a selected task is available, then an idle employee will take it. Of the other three, *Manage the company*, *Promote the store*, and *Solicit donations*, only one can be selected at a time. If the employee would be idle, then they will do this task. Then if another job becomes available from the previous three then they will take it, suspending the previous one.

By fulfilling tasks, the player can increase the available budget and expand the company. A timer is shown on the top of the screen, it starts at 15 minutes. The game is over when it stops, and the player is shown the current state of the company.

The most important task of the player in the end is to create an efficient team. The interviews are the primary means of this and the performance of the team during the game is a helpful indicator. Additional scoring is based on the number of tasks fulfilled, generated revenue etc., but this is just to differentiate between players who ended up with the identical teams.

P2M4 3 Data collection

During the game the player interactions are recorded and logged for future analysis. The data is timestamped. The following data is logged:

- Emotibit logs
- chat history with each applicant
- discovered traits and values of the applicants
- user interaction done by the player (like changing chat window, hiring someone, or assigning jobs)
- the final team and statistics (that are also displayed at the end of the game to the player)

One log file is generated for each session (that can include multiple playthroughs). The file is continuously saved and updated as the game progresses. The Emotibit and game logs are stored separately.

P2M4 4 User manual

The e-DIPLOMA Allies app received significant visual, control, and feedback upgrades during the post-evaluation adaptation phase of the project, while the basic gameplay mechanics remained unchanged. This section explains how the final version of the game works. The game is optimized for FullHD screen with 16:9 aspect ratio. After startup the following screen greets the player:

Figure P2M4.124 After selecting "Play" the game is started

Figure P2M4.125 Main game screen

The game scene is divided into **four** distinct sections (Figure P2M4.125). At the very top is the title bar, which mainly contains control buttons for additional dropdown windows, as well as other global game metrics. Just below this title bar, still at the top, is the **animation bar**, where the worker characters carry out their assigned tasks. On the lower left side is the global company **conflict chat window**. Any conflicts that arise between characters will appear in this window. To its right is the main gameplay area, where you can see the **cards of the hired workers** and assign them to various tasks.

The **three dropdown windows** realize different aspects of the team management task, each of which is introduced in detail below.

Figure P2M4.126 Title bar

One of the most important elements in the title bar (Figure P2M4.126) is the **Job Market** dropdown. This opens the **Job Market window** is where you can interview characters and hire them. On the far left of the title bar, you'll find the **Milestones** button. Clicking it opens the **Milestones window**, where you can track the progress of various objectives. On the right side of the title bar is the **Conflict window**, where you can monitor conflicts that arise between hired characters.

Between the buttons that control the dropdown windows, the first one from the left displays the **Company Organization Level**, which is primarily influenced by the *Manage Office* task. To its right is the **Company Prestige Level**, represented on a five-star scale. This is mainly affected by the *Promote* task and the number of *products sold*. Finally, to the right of that is the **Current Budget**, which determines your ability to hire new characters for work.

Figure P2M4.127 Job Market window

When the game scene first opens, the **Job Market** window (Figure P2M4.127) automatically drops down, as this is where the player will perform the first interactions. You can also open/close this window by

clicking on the Job Market button in the title bar. On the left side of the window, you'll find animated character cards. These cards enlarge and rotate when hovered over with the cursor. The currently selected character for conversation is highlighted with a red outline, while characters who have already been hired will have a green background.

In the center of the window is the chat section, where you can talk to the characters. To do so, type a question into the input field at the bottom and send it. It's important to note that spamming questions is not allowed—while the character is thinking, a thinking circle appears in the top-right corner. You can only ask another question once the circle disappears. During these conversations, you can get to know the character better, discover their traits, and negotiate their salary. This is a key part of the game, which is why several milestones are tied to these actions. On the right side of the window, you can see the selected character's attributes, and in the bottom corner, you'll find the **Hire** button, which allows you to add the character to your team. This is also where you can dismiss a character from your team. In that case, the Hire button changes to a **Dismiss** button.

Figure P2M4.128 Milestones window

Players need to **complete milestones**. These milestones can be viewed in the Milestones window (Figure P2M4.128), which can be opened and closed by clicking the Milestones button in the title bar. The window displays eight card-like milestones, each based on one of the core aspects of the game. These are:

1. Reach Company Organization Level 5
2. Reach 4.5 stars in Company Prestige
3. Sell 30 products
4. Discover 15 hidden traits on characters
5. Negotiate \$5 off a character's wage
6. Have a team consisting of at least 5 characters
7. Achieve an average team happiness of at least level 1 (smiling face)
8. Ensure there are no active conflicts within the team

Figure P2M4.129 Game finished window

When all milestones are completed, the game comes to an end, and a congratulations window (Figure P2M4.129) will appear to celebrate the player's achievement. After this, the player has the option to continue playing, but if they click the "No" button, the game will end and transition to the statistics summary window.

Figure P2M4.130 Conflict window

The third dropdown opens the **Conflict Window** (Figure P2M4.130), which can be shown or hidden by clicking the Conflicts button located on the right side of the title bar. The Conflict Window visualizes the conflicts between currently hired characters, but only to an extent that prevents players from easily identifying the exact values or traits causing the issues. The conflict window is divided into two main panels.

The **Relationship Panel** displays how characters relate to one another. In the center, you'll find a conflict graph that dynamically adjusts based on the size of the team. A **red line** indicates that the two connected characters have more conflicts than similarities. A **green line** means they share more compatible values than conflicting ones. A **yellow line** represents an equal number of matching and conflicting values. Below the graph, a card-style breakdown displays these values numerically for each character pair. At the top of this panel, you'll see the total number of conflicts and shared values across the entire team.

The **Filtered Graph Panel** shows a filtered version of the conflict graph, which visualizes character relationships based on specific values. A connection between two characters is shown only if they are in conflict based on the value pairs selected in the filter panel at the bottom.

Figure P2M4.131 Conflict window

Conflict messages between hired characters appear in a separate, chat-like panel. This panel is located on the left side of the game scene. This panel functions similarly to the chat window introduced in the Job Market, but here the user can only filter messages, not interact directly.

There are two main types of filtering available: By clicking the filter button on the left side, the **character filter** panel will appear. In this panel, if a character's color is **green**, their messages are **visible** in the chat. If their color is **red**, their messages are **hidden**. **Message content filtering** allows users to filter based on the actual content of the messages. You can search by values, character names, or any custom text to narrow down the messages shown.

Figure P2M4.132 Hired employee card

Each hired character has a double-sided card (Figure P2M4.132), displayed in a grid layout on the right side of the game scene. On the **front side** of the card, you can assign tasks to the worker. There are two main types of tasks.

Background Tasks are tasks that the character performs when no on-demand task is active. Only one background task can be assigned at a time. There are three possible background tasks:

1. Promote Store
2. Manage Office
3. Solicit Donations

These are represented by icons located at the top center of the character card.

On-Demand Tasks are tasks that can be freely selected, but only one can be active at a time. On-demand tasks override background tasks while they are in progress. They include:

4. Sell Goods
5. Stock Shelves
6. Deliver Goods

Their icons appear at the bottom center of the card. The selected task is highlighted with a thick black outline, while the currently active task is shown with a red outline. Task progress is visualized as a green circular progress indicator wrapping around the selected task's icon. If a background task is interrupted, its progress circle turns gray, and will only turn green again when the character resumes that task.

On the right side of the card, there are three buttons. The purple **Chat Button** opens the Job Market window and automatically selects the corresponding character, allowing you to continue the conversation or even dismiss them from the team. The **Flip Button** flips the card to reveal its back side. The red **"X" Button** aborts the currently active on-demand task, but only if it is running without being actively selected.

On the left side of the card, you'll find the character's portrait, and two icons above it. On the right: the character's current satisfaction/happiness status. On the left: a link to their animation element in the animation bar. Each icon includes a tooltip that appears when you hover the mouse over it for a moment, these provide helpful in-game information.

The **back side** of the double-sided Hired Employee card displays the character's relevant values and discovered traits. Clicking the green button flips the card back to its front side.

Figure P2M4.133 Animation Bar and Job Flow Overview

One of the key visual components of the game is the animation bar, which displays animated characters performing their assigned tasks in real time. This bar is located at the top of the game scene and helps players track active workers visually, in sync with their task progress. The animation bar is divided into six main sections, each associated with a building or work zone. From left to right, the buildings are: Office (Manage), Customer Apartment (Promote store), Store (Sell goods), Warehouse (Stock shelves), "Road" (Delivery goods), Charitable People's House (Solicit donations).

Each zone is visually supported by **icon-coded tooltips** at the top of the bar for quick identification. Characters perform their jobs either inside or next to these buildings, depending on the task type. Each task has a corresponding animation that reflects the actual work being done and its progress in real time. The movement speed of animated characters directly corresponds to their in-game task progress speed.

The game features a chain of jobs that are closely connected, both in gameplay and animation:

Solicit Donations – Characters stand near the Charitable People's House, slightly moving while asking for donations. Upon task completion, an animated donor appears, exiting the building with a box and placing it beside the house. These boxes represent donation packages.

Deliver Goods – These boxes are picked up by characters in delivery roles, who drive them to the Warehouse. Packages are animated accordingly.

Stock Shelves – Donation boxes from the warehouse, which contain one of five possible goods (T-shirt, book, teddy bear, shoes, or cap), are transported by handtruck into the Store by a character. They are then placed on shelves.

Sell Goods – Once goods are available in the store and customers appear on the right side of the apartment building, characters assigned to selling tasks run out of the store with products in hand to deliver them to the waiting customers.

The **Promote Store** task also plays a key role in this chain, as it continuously increases company prestige. Prestige can also rise through successful deliveries and sales. When prestige is high and products are available, new customers appear, meaning Sale tasks are generated automatically.

Each of these animated tasks contributes to the flow of goods through the system, and the entire chain is represented on the animation bar in real time.

Above each package, you'll see task icons with counters indicating how many pending tasks remain. If the number of pending tasks exceeds 5, the related task icon starts to pulse, signaling urgency. If a task is aborted or the character is dismissed, the corresponding animation immediately disappears from the bar.

Characters assigned to Manage Office stand in the Office and shout "Work! Work!" Characters working on **Promote Store** are positioned below the Customer Apartment, shouting "Buy! Buy!" to attract customers.

Players can freely reassign characters to different jobs at any time during gameplay. This is particularly useful early in the game when the team is still small and resources are limited. Each worker has traits and preferences that affect their performance:

Eager workers progress faster across all roles, while **Lazy workers** are slower.

Organizers excel in managing and stocking.

Lone Wolves function well independently, whereas **Team Players** rely more on good team dynamics.

Non-drivers perform poorly in delivery roles.

Follower characters thrive in high-organization environments but should not be placed in managerial roles.

Characters also have preferred and disliked job types, impacting their performance. These tendencies can be uncovered by talking with them in the Job Market. Preferences often align with broader personality traits like **Field Worker**, **Office Worker**, **Introvert**, or **Extrovert**.

When all milestones are completed, the game ends, and the statistics screen (Figure P2M4.134) appears. It shows the performance of the player. Average job efficiency and average job coverage is the most important. They indicate how well the player put together the team. The player can start a new game with the Restart button or quit.

Figure P2M4.134 End of game screen

P2M5. Angels – Social Product Management and Marketing

e-DIPLOMA **Angels** is an online board game played by four players featuring an underlying market simulation. It teaches financing options, market research, product positioning, and marketing in a learning-by-doing manner. These options are represented by cards, with a choice between several cards being the main mechanism in the game. Making this choice can be based on the knowledge displayed on the cards in the form of imagery, short catchphrases, but also slightly more detailed tooltip explanations. While playing the game is a group activity, it is a competitive game simulating market dynamics, where outcompeting rivals or following leaders could be fruitful strategies.

P2M5 1 Technology

e-DIPLOMA **Angels** is implemented as a client-server web application. The server application must run on a computer that can either be on-premises or in the cloud. Clients run in browsers, with Google Chrome used for development, test, and piloting activities. Both the client and server software was developed in Kotlin, built using the Gradle build system, compiled using the Kotlin multiplatform plugin, with the server compiled into a Node.js executable, and the client into a JavaScript executable. They communicate through WebSocket connections.

Angels can be launched from the e-DIPLOMA platform. The user is redirected to the URL of the server endpoint from where the browser instantly downloads the client code in form of JavaScript files.

P2M5 2 Activity flow

P2M5 2.1 Gameplay structure

The game consists of *rounds*. Each round consists of *phases*. The first round one has a single, *starting* phase. In this, players cannot perform any action, but they can navigate the play area, hover the mouse over game elements, and read corresponding tooltips. They learn about the basics of the game in this phase. Later rounds all consist of three phases:

- *Carousel phase*: a set of cards rotates slowly over the game area. Players can pick cards that are in the quarter of the carousel closest to them, as long as they have enough *picks*. Cards represent business development opportunities, and the number of picks depends on the financing and sales the player has. Picked cards move to the player's hand.
- *Planning phase*: players can, independently, play any number of cards from their hands. These actions are not revealed to the other players.
- *Sales phase*: the results of the actions are evaluated and displayed to all players. Sales are performed and tallied.

P2M5 2.2 The market

The game is played in a fictitious city, with four districts, represented by textured discs. Every district has 36 representative citizens, represented by pawns. All citizens can be categorized into six groups along seven social statistics. The statistics and their representative icons are:

Health	Income	Education	Social connectedness	Technical aptitude	Happiness	Age

With appropriate *Market Segmentation* cards, pawns can be ordered in districts according to their levels in any one of the social statistics. In every turn, every citizen is looking to improve one of its social statistics. Therefore, it is looking for a product or service that contributes to that statistic. Using appropriate *Market Research* cards, pawns can be colored to indicate this demand.

Every player has an area on the table where they can set up their business. This consists of the *Research*, *Financing*, and *Brand* areas.

P2M5 2.2.1 Research area

This area shows the icons of the social statistics. The player can play market research cards, dragging them from their hand onto the icons, thereby enabling them to see demand or perform market segmentation.

P2M5 2.2.2 Financing area

The player can drag financing cards here. How many opportunities (card picks) per round are financed is shown here, as well as the results of sales.

P2M5 2.2.3 Brands area

The player can build their business, or businesses, by playing cards to this area. Every brand is either a product or a service. Brand cards played represent the capability to manufacture or provide said product or service. Other cards, including distribution cards like *Store*, or promotion cards like *Influencers*, can be played onto the brand cards, thereby enhancing the business with some capability or boosting it with some market effect.

P2M5 2.3 Cards

P2M5 2.3.1 Financing

Financing cards provide opportunities, meaning pick of cards in the Carousel phase. Every card specifies the number of picks provided, and *victory points* provided when some conditions are met. There are equity-based financing cards, like *Angel Investor*, *Crowdfunding*, or *Venture Capital*, that offer more picks on completing a given number of sales, and there are government funding cards, that offer double victory points on sales improving a certain social statistic. The latter include *Education Grant* and *Cultural Grant*, as examples. The game is won by the player who gathers the most victory points, representing the largest social impact in the targeted statistic.

P2M5 2.3.2 Market research

Market research cards include *Survey Demand* and *Market Segmentation*. These cards must be dropped on stat icons in the Research Area, whereupon a token appears over the icon. Surveying demand for a kind of social statistic reveals to the player, by coloring the pawns representing the customers, which citizens would buy products promoting that stat. Market segmentation gives the player the ability, by clicking the appropriate icon, to separate citizens according to their level in a given statistic. This makes it possible to do promotion in a targeted manner.

P2M5 2.3.3 Brands

Brand cards represent some a capability to manufacture some product or provide some service. All the products and services in the game are such that they provide for customer needs in two social stats. For example, *Student Loan* would help with both *Education* and *Wealth*, while *Dating Size* would promote *Social Connectedness* and *Happiness*. While some of the cards, like *Soccer Ball* or *Amphetamine*, are less serious, other cards like *Food Sharing* or *Matchmaker* depict genuine social enterprises, and some like *Charity* or *Online Diagnosis* offer subtle social commentary. Brands should be played to the Brands Area, and all other cards that are not financing, research, or brand cards, must be played on a brand card to endow the business with new capabilities. The social stats a product caters for are important, as only those customers are going to buy the product, who have the corresponding demand (as revealed by market research discussed above).

P2M5 2.3.4 Promotion

Promotions are the primary means to divert the attention of people towards our products and services. Promotion cards can be played on brands to generate an advertisement token. These tokens can be dropped on zones to select where these advertisements should be focused on. If the player has Market Segmentation researched then they can segment the population there and use targeted advertisement to focus a specific social segment.

P2M5 2.3.5 Distribution channels

Distribution cards represent opportunities and investments in local venues to setup stores and services in. These cards can be dropped on brands which in turn generates a store token. This token can be dropped on zones to establish a local venue. District residents will visit these stores based on their preferences and use the services or buy the products. The number of stores present in a district limits the availability of the brand therefore more stores can be established to expand the reach.

P2M5 3 User manual

When the game starts you are presented with the game board (Figure P2M5.135). Top and bottom left shows a tooltip and card view of the currently hovered card (or element). The current round and player state is indicated on the top right. The player area is in front of the player, separated into 4 areas and a deck of cards. Your hand is shown on the bottom.

Each player has their own player area where they can activate cards. Each round you draw 2 cards and can also draw a few cards from the carousel at the start of the turn. The number of cards drawn from the carousel is the active Euro icons in your Financing area.

Figure P2M5.135 The game board

Your goal is to select and then build up your **brand** by building **stores** and **marketing** your products or services to the citizens. Districts are separate and you can build stores in multiple districts to reach a wider audience.

You can **activate cards by dragging and dropping** them over their respective areas (or cards). Some cards generate tokens this way. Tokens can be dragged and dropped over the districts to activate them (building stores or marketing).

Figure P2M5.136 Dropping a card onto the Brand area

Each round you will first draw some cards from the carousel then play your cards and finally see the result and scoring. If you finished your turn you can end the round by clicking on the Finish phase button in the top right.

During the first round you will draw **Financing cards** from the carousel. You should activate it to draw more cards during subsequent rounds.

Figure P2M5.137 An activated financing card

In your starting hand you will also find **Market Segmentation** and **Survey cards**. These can be activated by dropping them on an icon in the **Research area**. Survey will reveal which citizens are demanding the selected statistic. Market Segmentation will create a clickable triangle token on the icon that can be used to group the citizens according to that stat. You should use these before the second round starts.

Figure P2M5.138 Market research cards and the Research area

Figure P2M5.139 Activated market segmentation

During the second round **Brand cards** can be drawn from the carousel. Each brand has two statistics that they provide to the citizens. You should choose a brand based on your market research in the previous round. It will define your strategy for the game.

Figure P2M5.140 An activated brand card with store tokens

During the planning phase you should activate the brand card that you got by dropping it onto your brand area. You can also build a store by dropping a store card onto the activated brand card. The store can be built on any district by dropping the token on it. You should use market research to find which district is the best choice. Marketing cards can be used to advertise you brand to a group of people. First drop the marketing card onto the brand to create a marketing token. Then activate your market segmentation for a relevant stat, to group the citizens. Find a group that should receive the marketing and drop the token onto this group (the slice of the district under the group).

Figure P2M5.141 Building a store

Figure P2M5.142 A brand with a marketing token

Figure P2M5.143 Advertising to a group of customers

After the planning phase the game will calculate the impact and result of your actions. If you made sales, it impacts the citizens in the district and you will also gain score.

Figure P2M5.144 Sales area

In the fourth round a second financing option can be drawn from the carousel. It is a **Government Grant** that provides additional victory points if you do sales in a certain statistic.

Figure P2M5.145 A government grant card

Sometimes additional brand cards can be drawn in later rounds, but you should focus on at most 3 brands. Building only one brand in the game is also perfectly viable. Do not forget to expand in multiple districts.

P2M5 4 Event recording

e-Diploma Angels is implemented as an online game that runs in the browser. The browser cannot connect to the Emotibit by itself therefore it needs a separate companion application. This application is written in Unity just like the main application for some other modules. It is installed in the same way as the rest. It has two main objectives:

First it establishes a connection to the Emotibit and continuously logs the incoming data. Secondly it starts up a local WebSocket server. The web application connects to this server and sends the game logs continuously. The received data is continuously logged in the same way as the Emotibit data.

The web application sends messages after the connection is established. The event type of messages describes direct user interactions with the game in the browser. Stat type messages send the current score of the player and signal that the game has ended. This in turn finalizes the logs stored on the computer and automatically closes this companion application.

Additionally, the application has a graphical display that shows the current state of the connected user and the Emotibit.

Quit

Emotibit connecting...

Waiting for player...

e-DIPLOMA

Figure P2M5.146 Companion application

P3. VR Education

P3M1 1 Learning material

P3M1 1.1 Knowledge

This course prototype targets current but also future educators and covers advantages and disadvantages of VR environments. It is supported by lectures coupled to practical experiences in VR. Typical activities in VR can be learned first-hand and it helps users to familiarize themselves with these tools and metaphors. Some of the technologies employed also constitute novel solutions (e.g., the visualization method or the indications for collaboration). Due to its intended generality, this prototype was built to be independent of a particular area and will focus on various elements in VR.

The module uses different applications to teach skillsets in a playful manner. As in the original prototype outline, the following topics are addressed:

- Introductory information in P3M1 3.1
- Interaction (grabbing, scaling, pointing...) in P3M1 3.2
- Navigation (teleporting, smooth motion, minimaps...) in P3M1 3.3
- Visualization (standard shading models, abstract shading, lighting, composition...) in P3M1 3.4
- Collaboration (movement imitation with various examples) in P3M1 3.5
- Advanced aspects (interactive experience of simulation of gravity and physical properties) in P3M1 3.6

P3M1 1.2 Competencies

Participants in this course will gain knowledge of VR technology and its possibilities. They will learn about VR in general and become able to judge the most appropriate options for their own teaching activities. They will also be able to identify common pitfalls in VR education and increase their awareness with regards to inherent limitations. They will further develop an understanding of how one can design educational material for a virtual reality environment. Furthermore, they will learn about some new possibilities that VR can bring new possibilities to the educational context.

P3M1 2 Activity specification

P3M1 2.1 Concept

The main target was to integrate the learning in a playful manner by allowing the user to engage in the form of minigames or experiences. As one of our goals was to also evaluate new techniques, these elements could then also serve as a benchmark to gain insights into their practical value. analyse effectiveness of new solutions. Specifically, the activities were chosen to reflect common solutions in existing VR applications.

P3M1 3 Final activity flow

P3M1 3.1 Introduction: passive

This element constitutes a short overview session of VR/AR and the related technology, as illustrated in Figure P2M5.147. The corresponding video will be made available on the Moodle platform and is currently provided as a download (see below).

Figure P2M5.147 A frame from the introductory video

P3M1 3.2 Interaction: passive + active

This element explores the use of VR controllers to interact with virtual objects. It starts with a lecture that covers the basics and gives an outlook on new technology. The interactive part takes the form of a minigame, where the scenario is a Kindergarten, in which the user needs to place virtual objects in predefined locations. In some cases, these objects need to undergo transformations, like rotations or scaling. In all situations, the software focuses on standard mechanisms to ensure a wide applicability in other contexts. The active HMD components cover 5 activities; stacking of objects (teaching grabbing and placing), telegrabbing (teaching stationary interaction with distant objects), Orientation (teaching rotations and placement), Gesture interaction (two examples). Figure P2M5.148 shows the application. The Kindergarten setting helps evoke familiarity with the learning of interactions among the users.

Figure P2M5.148 Screenshots from the interaction application

P3M1 3.3 Navigation: passive + active

This element starts with a lecture on navigation techniques. It covers practical, as well as theoretical insights. The supporting HMD activity is presented as a mini game with several stages, in which a user acts as a shepherd and needs to navigate a virtual environment to bring sheep to predefined locations. The difficulty arises from the fact that the sheep cannot be directly impacted but are indirectly affected by the user. Whenever the user is close enough to a sheep, it will move away in the opposite direction. In consequence, the user builds up the necessary competencies to navigate the environment. The game consists of several levels, each making use of different typical navigation metaphors; smooth motion, teleporting, minimap, or flying.

Figure P2M5.149 shows screenshots from the Navigation application. The game is easy to grasp, but difficult to master for VR beginners. The user needs to chase the sheep into their barns, using different navigation techniques. Hereby, they are playfully learning and experiencing the different methods and understand their advantages and disadvantages.

Figure P2M5.149 Screenshots from the Navigation application

P3M1 3.4 Visualization: passive + active

This element focuses on the fact that virtual scenes recreated with 3D graphics require us to define light sources and materials. These have a huge impact on the appearance of the environment. For example, a light source placed at the position of the observer will eliminate most of the surface cues. We start with a short lecture explaining the basics of lighting and object appearance. This is followed by an interactive experience. Here, a user will first position, then illuminate a car and play with different lighting settings. Further, they can explore a non-realistic depiction.

Figure P2M5.150 The townsquare area

The townsquare (Figure P2M5.150) is an area in which a user is sequentially introduced to different lighting and material interactions. The user can influence the time of the day and observe the effect of different light configurations.

We also used this implementation as a basis for our exploration of the visualization style on the effectiveness on recognition and memorization tasks, which was prepared as a research paper. In the next interactive element, the user is transported into a stadium, where they need to work on the lighting of an object to represent it in an effective manner.

In Figure P2M5.151, the left illustration shows a search game that depicts a stylized rendering style. The right image shows the car show, at which the user is asked to influence the light to best depict the car.

Figure P2M5.151 Stylized rendering (left) and the car show (right)

P3M1 3.5 Collaboration: passive + active

In VR, users are not necessarily located in the same physical space. Interaction is therefore more difficult to achieve. The lecture first talks about problems of co-locating people in the form of avatars together in virtual environments and gives an overview of some of the techniques to guide attention.

After this passive part, the user can then experience examples of related techniques. The first asks users to imitate a given motion by a virtual avatar and to remember the motion that is initiated. Such “ghost instructors” have shown to be very effective for motion/action learning. The task is repeated a few times and the accuracy of the user is measured. Upon this basis, we also explored novel schemes, to see if it can generate a benefit for the learning of the motion, which was prepared as a research paper.

In another experience, the user is able to perceive the impact of comfort zones in VR. In the real world, we keep a natural distance from one another and these zones translate to VR. The user can explore this effect with a virtual avatar. The avatar uses different facial expressions and facial animations, which are important for immersion, but such expressed emotions can also influence our comfort zones. Especially, when a face appears uncanny to a user, it might affect our preferred distance. To investigate the latter point, also different rendering styles are explored. To enable diversity, the application opted for a rather gender-neutral face with different ethnicities. In a final application, as an alternative to avatar-based interaction, a highlighting scheme is shown that illustrates how to guide users and their gaze in VR by the help of indicators.

In Figure P2M5.152, in the top row, a “ghost instructor” shows hand motion that the user is asked to imitate (left). A walkthrough of a tomb with highlighted details helps users understand how guidance in a VR experience can be performed without an actual instructor. In the lower row, a virtual face can be controlled by the user and placed at different distances. Rendering style, expression, animation and familiarity are among the different factors that influence our comfort zone.

Figure P2M5.152 Ghost instructor and virtual face

P3M1 3.6 Demonstration of Advanced Aspects: passive + active

This element explores the use of VR in an innovative fashion. As this topic is very broad, the initial lecture focuses on a few examples and the following activity also picks one particular use case. Here, the user is on different planets, where they can test the bouncing behavior of different types of sport balls, ranging from soccer to tennis and bowling.

The simulation is physically-based and takes air resistance, weight, and elasticity into account. It is possible to accelerate or stop time, change the viewpoint, change gravity, size or weight, and more. In this way, the forces that act on objects can be learned about in an explorative manner. Several existing planets and locations have been implemented, including Earth, Mars, the Moon etc. It can serve as an inspiration to other teachers to consider novel ways to teach theoretical skills and present experiments that would be unattainable otherwise.

Physics are not always easy to understand. Instead of learning about the many factors that influence the bouncing behavior of a ball, the users can explore the effect directly (Figure P2M5.153) – on different planets (left – Earth), with custom ball attributes, or even on a virtual planet (right), where the conditions (such as gravity) can be influenced by the user.

Figure P2M5.153 *Physics simulation*

P3M1 3.7 Final Project: A virtual museum: passive + active

This part is initiated with a very short video, mostly intended to conclude the other lectures. The users receive a detailed written manual that they can refer to in order to complete the final project. The manual is provided together with the application itself, as supplementary material to this report.

This stage of the course enables users to design their own 3D VR environment. The inspiration for this application is a virtual museum that can be populated with different models, e.g., with respect to a certain educational topic. The software enables the use of new objects from online resources, which can be integrated directly by a teacher. This makes it possible to generate many very different and personalized experiences. The prototype still comes with a few predefined models to allow everyone to follow the activity, but the manual describes the integration of new objects. The creation process has many facets and involves the previously experienced core techniques that can now be used in a creative fashion. Users layout a floor plan, place walls or barriers, as well as paint and color the environment. Next, they can place objects and light sources to complete their designs. Afterwards, they define navigation metaphors. For example, allow teleporting to certain locations (e.g., a point of interest in front of an exhibited object) or to enable the possibility to fly in certain locations (e.g., to examine a large statue). The user can iterate between the different stages if needed. The design takes place at a scale in which the user is much enlarged. This enables them to obtain an overview of the entire environment.

The last activity of the course is the design of a virtual museum (Figure P2M5.154). In the editing stage, a user can place objects, define navigation attributes, lighting, highlighting mechanisms, and even color

elements to their liking. The integration of arbitrary objects enables a wide variety of creations. Finally, the designed museum experience can be shared and visited by others.

Figure P2M5.154 Virtual museum

The actual museum visit takes place in the game mode (Figure P2M5.155), where the user is seamlessly shrunk to the scale of the virtual museum and can then test the walkthrough. Specifically, it is possible to place interactive elements that are triggered, when the user passes over certain areas to guide the virtual visitors. The resulting museum design can be shared with other users. It also means that users can save their work and continue at a latter point to further refine their designs. Such a concept of a virtual museum can be an interesting element to grow a potential e-Diploma community around in the future.

Figure P2M5.155 Game mode

P3M1 4 Monitoring

The navigation and interaction applications have been refined to record various data during the execution. Besides the user-centric data, such as heartbeat, eye movement, and 6DOF head and controller movement (similar to the details provided in Prototype 2). Additionally, the applications do capture accurate eye tracking with the help of pupil trackers. The gaze is mapped into the scene and objects and gaze interaction with objects of importance is captured next to the general eye motion, including when the gaze enters and leaves the object zones. Other interactions with objects, as well as objects of interest themselves are observed and their locations and orientations registered. These data recordings are application-dependent but enable tracking of the users actions in the virtual environment for analysis purposes. A timer in the sessions is also recorded, in case that a captured video footage needs alignment. Further, the integration of secondary sensors, like the Emotibit has been realized (the mechanism and design is similar to Prototype 2 and will therefore not be repeated here). All captured data is ultimately merged into a single data file that encodes the session, including potential supplementary information about the users. This integrated file facilitates the session analysis. In this prototype, all data is locally

handled. The creative design part at the end of the course, supports storing the resulting creation. In principle, this can become another interesting element of data to analyze as well. Initially binary, all data is now encoded in human-readable format to enable easy parsing.

P3M1 5 Technical documentation

P3M1 5.1 Employed technologies

The application has been created in Unity 2023. The software mainly targets the headset HP Reverb G2 Omnicept, which was chosen by the consortium, due to its various functionalities in terms of data capture. The software does retrieve the information to the fullest capacity. This information includes among others, eye tracking data, gaze, and heartbeat. Furthermore, the prototype is accompanied by secondary software in C# to capture information from an Emotibit sensor. This hardware has sensors to provide additional user data. The incoming data stream is aligned and integrated in the data summarization that is executed in the background. This generated file is a human-readable CSV file, which was formatted to match the analysis requirements of the other partners.

P3M1 5.2 Algorithms and methods

Besides standard techniques, the prototype builds upon several newly-developed solutions for visualization, interaction, and collaboration. Some are in preparation for a scientific submission and intended to contribute to the goal of establishing some best-practice insights, as targeted by the E-Diploma project. In this context, studies are planned as part of the pilot to test related hypotheses. These behind-the-scenes workings are not of direct relevance for the functionality of the prototype and related course but can, if successful, certainly contribute positively to it.

To provide an example, we developed a new visualization method that is already used in the prototypes. It allows us to obtain high-quality, yet efficient illustrations. Existing methods would not have given the same visual quality. Further, it allowed us to integrate a performance adjustment in the software. Hereby, our course can be used on machines with different performance capacities. The provided software can be launched with different batch files that can be used to configure the visual quality.

P3M1 6 Software design overview

P3M1 6.1 Implementation

The software components were fully written in C# and built within Unity. For the integration with the HP Omnicept their HP Glia API was integrated. The Unity event handlers capture application-specific events. The Emotibit is followed via an external program, which was built to ensure that it can also be used when testing non-VR educational settings. The programs exchange time information to ensure that data stays aligned and can be correctly associated. The VR interface is abstracted by mapping functionality from OpenXR. Hereby, different headsets can be supported without having to make too many adjustments. New algorithms have partially been developed in independent frameworks to overcome potential restrictions

that are due to the underlying game engine. Their results have then been transferred, once tested and the design settled upon. Some additional applications were developed to explore other directions but these developments were not included, as they are not of direct relevance to the course content.

P3M1 7 Demonstration

P3M1 7.1 Deployment

The course content will be integrated into the Moodle platform in the following months, as outlined in the proposal. At this point, the course can be fully accessed via the following open link:
<https://surfdive.surf.nl/files/index.php/s/sTpSGsk4hSv3x4s>

The course content will be integrated into the Moodle platform in the future, as outlined in the proposal. At this point, it has been submitted as a zipped executable. Both the main course activities and the final activity for building the interactive museum are provided in VR-Education.zip.

P3M1 7.2 Requirements

The program runs on a Windows 11 system, where the main bottleneck is the graphics card performance. We developed different versions of the software for low-budget PCs, around an NVIDIA GTX 2080, and high-end setups, including an NVIDIA GTX 4090. The program was designed to allow these fine-grained controls by integrating different settings for, e.g., resolutions, shader precision, and field of view. These can be controlled via the corresponding launch scripts.

P3M1 8 User instructions

To avoid any user influence, as it is intended as a remotely executed software, all instructions are directly integrated into the application itself in the form of text boxes that accompany the user experience. The exception is the last part of the course. The final project is initiated with a written document. The reason is that this last application is relatively complex, and it is more convenient for a user to receive a reference manual. Furthermore, the document also tests if the users have learned to read such technical descriptions and are able to understand the concepts after following the course.

P3M1 9 Internal testing results

The software has been tested successfully with different headset types (HP Reverb G2 Omnicept, HTC Vive Pro Eye/2, Meta Quest 2/Pro/3) and many users (in total more than 70 users have already tested the software or participated in studies related to this course platform). We used some of these tests for measuring the effectiveness of the newly proposed solutions, which will be reported on in the best-practices report that will be submitted by the end of the project.

7 Source code and deployed service access

All three prototypes are completely integrated with the e-DIPLOMA Platform, and embedded in the e-DIPLOMA Moodle course pages, available at <https://cg.iit.bme.hu:3004>. Please apply for an appropriate (student or teacher) account at e-DIPLOMA Moodle administrator László Szécsi (szecsi@iit.bme.hu).

7.1 Prototype 1

Access and sustainability

All modules of Prototype 1 are accessible through e-DIPLOMA Moodle at <https://cg.iit.bme.hu:3004>. The e-DIPLOMA Moodle site, as well as underlying infrastructure in the AWS cloud is maintained by e-DIPLOMA partner BME, administrators are László Szécsi (szecsi@iit.bme.hu) and András Fridvalszky (fridvalszky@iit.bme.hu). Prototype 1 courses and on-premises servers for Module 5 are maintained by UJI (Immaculada Remolar Quintana, remolar@uji.es).

The source code of Modules 2, 4 and 5 are available in the following GitHub repositories:

Virtual Playground: Explore Block Coding in Virtual Reality (Module 2):

<https://github.com/initUJI/e-DIPLOMA-p1-m2.git>

ARduino Learn: Practice with Microcontroller and Components (Module 4):

<https://github.com/initUJI/e-DIPLOMA-p1-m4.git>

Collaborative Virtual Reality Codeventure (Module 5):

<https://github.com/initUJI/e-DIPLOMA-p1-final-project.git>

The repositories are private for reasons of licensing, security, and exploitation of the results. For access, apply via email to e-diploma@uji.es, indicating your GitHub username, which modules you wish to access, and the reason for doing so.

The videos of Modules 1 and 3 can be found on YouTube by accessing the following links:

Module 1:

What's Programming All About?

<https://youtu.be/EzetFg1vlal>

Loops: the Repeaters of Coding

<https://youtu.be/anzVvh00mZE>

Conditionals: Making Decisions in Code

<https://youtu.be/KrvE7KEzflI>

Integrating What we Have Learned

<https://youtu.be/iU3AVTy0314>

Module 3:**First Steps into the World of Electronics**

<https://youtu.be/zPdAkVpZ5Js>

Connecting Arduino Sensors and Actuators

<https://youtu.be/xllLnCaB3X0>

All these resources also available through the e-DIPLOMA Moodle course page.

7.2 Prototype 2

Access and sustainability

All modules of Prototype 2 are accessible through **e-DIPLOMA Moodle** at <https://cg.iit.bme.hu:3004>. The e-DIPLOMA Moodle site, as well as underlying infrastructure in the AWS cloud is maintained by e-DIPLOMA partner BME, administrators are László Szécsi (szecsi@iit.bme.hu) and András Fridvalszky (fridvalszky@iit.bme.hu). Prototype 2 courses are maintained by László Szécsi (szecsi@iit.bme.hu). On-premise chatbot servers at BME have been discontinued, a commercial chatbot service (ChatGPT) account is maintained by BME instead. For Module 3, EC2 cloud servers with the associated Microsoft Teams license are maintained by e-DIPLOMA partner Brainstorm (Francisco Ibañez, francisco@brainstorm3d.com), conditional on the continued existence of demand for this service. It is foreseen that users completing Module 3 will instead opt for using the Edison OnCloud service, also provided by Brainstorm, using their own institutional Teams accounts.

The source code is available in the repositories on GitHub, under the organisation BME-IIT-CG (<https://github.com/BME-IIT-CG>). The repositories are private for reasons of licensing, security, and exploitation of the results. For access, apply via email to szecsi@iit.bme.hu, indicating your GitHub username, which tools or modules you wish to access, and the reason for doing so.

7.3 Prototype 3

Access and sustainability

All modules of Prototype 3 are accessible through **e-DIPLOMA Moodle** at <https://cg.iit.bme.hu:3004>. The e-DIPLOMA Moodle site, as well as underlying infrastructure in the AWS cloud is maintained by e-DIPLOMA partner BME, administrators are László Szécsi (szecsi@iit.bme.hu) and András Fridvalszky (fridvalszky@iit.bme.hu). Prototype 3 courses are maintained by TU Delft (Ricardo Guerra Marroquim, R.Marroquim@tudelft.nl).

The source code is available on GitHub (<https://github.com/e-DIPLOMA/Prototype-3>). The repositories are private for reasons of licensing, security, and exploitation of the results. For access, apply via email to R.Marroquim@tudelft.nl, indicating your GitHub username, which modules you wish to access, and the reason for doing so.

8 Conclusions

This document accompanies the software constituting deliverable D4.3 of the e-DIPLOMA project, which is delivered through repositories and access to the cloud-deployed platform. We described the work done on the e-DIPLOMA prototypes, specified the technical details, and gave a detailed overview of functionality and usage.

The prototypes in this demonstrator show that the courses have been developed to cover the intended learning material. They teach respective competencies using targeted disruptive technologies, including VR, AR, gaming, conversational AI, videoconferencing, and Edison AR-enhanced streaming. They are able to log activity events and can work along with equipment recording physiological data.

When originally delivered, the prototypes were ready for the later phases of the project, which included engaging the prototypes in user studies with the appropriate machinery for data capture, data management, and the ethics framework. These phases were successfully completed, as described in the respective deliverables. As part of task T4.3, T4.4, and T4.5, the prototypes also underwent further, post-evaluation adaptation following indications from the user studies, emerging best practices, or exploitation goals. The current document, alongside online documentation found in the repositories, reflects these changes.

9 References

[1] Krathwohl, D. R. "A Revision Bloom's Taxonomy: An Overview." *Theory into Practice* (2002).

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